

Supplementary material S1. Principaux synonymes courants des taxons listés

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14853741>

Mis en ligne le 12 février 2025 – voir l'article principal pour la liste complète et les références bibliographiques

Famille **Andrenidae** LATREILLE, 1802

Sous-famille **Andreninae** LATREILLE, 1802

Genre **Andrena** FABRICIUS, 1775

3. Andrena (Taeniandrena) afzeliella (KIRBY, 1802).

Melitta fuscata KIRBY, 1802 – *Andrena canescens* SCHENCK, 1853 – *Andrena albofasciata* THOMSON, 1870 – *Andrena afzeliella* var. *heliopolis* FRIESE, 1914 – *Andrena pseudovatula* ALFKEN, 1926.

6. Andrena (Micrandrena) alfkenella PERKINS, 1914.

Andrena moricella PERKINS, 1914.

15. Andrena (Andrena) apicata SMITH, 1847.

En France, l'espèce a souvent été confondue avec *Andrena batava* PÉREZ, 1902. Les deux sont considérées comme des taxons distincts à la répartition différente.

18. Andrena (Melandrena) assimilis Radoszkowski, 1876.

Andrena gallica SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883.

23. Andrena (Euandrena) bicolor FABRICIUS, 1775.

Andrena gwynana (KIRBY, 1802).

24. Andrena (Melandrena) bicolorata (ROSSI, 1790).

Andrena nigrocineria DESTEFANI, 1873 – *Andrena lichtensteini* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883.

25. Andrena (Plastandrena) bimaculata (KIRBY, 1802).

Andrena consobrina EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Andrena oligotricha* MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1952.

26. Andrena (Notandrena) binominata SMITH, 1853.

Andrena griseofusca PÉREZ, 1903 – *Andrena mallorcana* FRIESE, 1922.

32. Andrena (Melandrena) cineraria (LINNAEUS, 1758).

Andrena erythrocnemis MORAWITZ, 1871.

33. Andrena (Chlorandrena) cinerea BRULLÉ, 1832.

Andrena insula STRAND, 1921 – *Andrena arcuata* PÉREZ, 1903 – *Andrena molesta* PÉREZ, 1903.

37. Andrena (Brachyandrena) colletiformis MORAWITZ, 1874.

Andrena dissidens SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883 – *Andrena nanana* STRAND, 1915 – *Andrena subsquamularis* NOSKIEWICZ, 1960.

45. Andrena (Distantandrena) distinguenda SCHENCK, 1871.

Espèce en partie notée sous le nom d'*Andrena obsoleta* PÉREZ, 1896 dans le travail de RASMONT *et al.* (1995).

46. Andrena (Micrandrena) djelfensis PÉREZ, 1895.

Andrena abstersa PÉREZ, 1903 – *Andrena depressiuscula* PÉREZ, 1903.

47. Andrena (Simandrena) dorsata (KIRBY, 1802).

Andrena allaria PÉREZ, 1903.

52. Andrena (Truncandrena) ferrugineicrus DOURS, 1872.

Andrena strigifrons PÉREZ, 1903.

53. Andrena (Holandrena) flavilabris SCHENCK, 1874.

Elle était auparavant considérée comme la forme printanière d'*A. decipiens* (SCHEUCHL & WILLNER, 2016).

58. Andrena (Lepidandrena) florivaga EVERS-MANN, 1852.

Andrena molhusina BLÜTGHEIN, 1914.

61. Andrena (Andrena) fulva (MÜLLER, 1766).

Andrena armata GMELIN, 1790 – *Andrena fulva* (SCHRANK, 1781).

63. Andrena (Euandrena) fulvata STÖCKHERT, 1930.

Andrena angustior fulvata WARNCKE *et al.*, 1974.

70. Andrena (Melandrena) gravida IMHOFF, 1832.

Andrena fasciata NYLANDER, 1852.

72. Andrena (Notandrena) griseobalteata DOURS, 1872.

Andrena commutata SCHULTZ, 1906, *Andrena erythrocnemis* auct. (*nec* MORAWITZ, 1871).

80. Andrena (Aenandrena) hystrix SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883.

Andrena opaciventris FRIESE, 1921.

85. Andrena (Biareolina) lagopus LATREILLE, 1809.

Andrena perezella (DOURS, 1873).

87. Andrena (Euandrena) lavandulae, PÉREZ, 1902.

Andrena impressa WARNCKE, 1967 – *A. angustior impressa* WARNCKE, 1967.

90. Andrena (Leucandrena) leptopyga PÉREZ, 1895.

Espèce notée sous le nom d'*Andrena maroccana* BENOIST, 1950 dans le travail de RASMONT *et al.* (1995).

91. Andrena (Chlorandrena) leucolippa PÉREZ, 1895.

Espèce notée sous le nom d'*Andrena boyerella* (DOURS, 1872) dans le travail de RASMONT *et al.*, 1995.

92. Andrena (Melandrena) limata SMITH, 1853.

Andrena pectoralis SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883, STÖCKHERT *in* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1930.

101. Andrena (Melandrena) morio BRULLÉ, 1832.

Andrena hispania WARNCKE, 1967.

102. Andrena (Didonia) mucida KRIECHBAUMER, 1873.

Andrena julliani SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883.

108. Andrena (Truncandrena) nigropilosa WARNCKE, 1967.

Andrena truncatilabris espanola WARNCKE, 1967.

109. Andrena (Plastandrena) nigrospina THOMSON, 1872.

110. Andrena (Melandrena) nitida (MÜLLER, 1776).

Andrena pubescens OLIVIER, 1789.

111. Andrena (Notandrena) nitidiuscula SCHENCK, 1853.

Andrena gascheti PÉREZ, 1903 – *Andrena petroselini* PÉREZ, 1903.

112. Andrena (Distantandrena) nitidula PÉREZ, 1903.

Andrena nitidella VIREECK, 1916.

127. Andrena (Plastandrena) pilipes FABRICIUS, 1781.

Andrena carbonaria auct. *nec* (LINNAEUS, 1767).

128. Andrena (Ulandrena) polita SMITH, 1847.

129. Andrena (Poecilandrena) potentillae PANZER, 1809.

Andrena genevensis SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883.

136. Andrena (incertae sedis) ranunculorum MORAWITZ, 1877.

Andrena setosa PÉREZ, 1903.

139. Andrena (Hoplandrena) rosae PANZER, 1801.

Andrena eximia SMITH, 1847 – *Andrena stragulata* ILLIGER, 1806.

Les spécimens d'*Andrena eximia* SMITH, 1847 mentionnés par RASMONT *et al.* (1995) sont aujourd'hui considérés comme correspondant à *Andrena rosae*.

141. Andrena (Lepidandrena) rufizona IMHOFF, 1834.

Andrena alpina MORAWITZ, 1872.

144. Andrena (Taeniandrena) russula LEPELETIER, 1841.

Andrena similis SMITH, 1849 – *Andrena rufohispida* DOURS, 1872.

146. Andrena (Suandrena) savignyi SPINOLA, 1838.

Andrena bipartita BRULLÉ, 1839.

149. Andrena (Hoplandrena) scotica PERKINS, 1916.

Andrena carantonica auct. *nec* PÉREZ, 1902.

Espèce notée sous le nom d'*Andrena sabulosa* (SCOPOLI, 1763) dans la liste de RASMONT *et al.*, 1995. Le nom d'*Andrena scotica* est le nom valide pour ce qui a été par le passé appelé *A. carantonica* (WOOD *et al.*, 2022). Toutefois le type d'*Andrena carantonica* est très probablement un spécimen d'*Andrena trimmerana*.

150. Andrena (Micrandrena) semilaevis PÉREZ, 1903.

Andrena saundersella PERKINS, 1914.

156. Andrena (Micrandrena) sprete PÉREZ, 1895.

Andrena curtula PÉREZ, 1903.

157. Andrena (Chlorandrena) stabiana MORICE, 1899.

Andrena emarginata PÉREZ, 1903.

163. Andrena (Tarsandrena) tarsata NYLANDER, 1848.

Andrena gentianae VACHAL, 1906.

164. Andrena (Micrandrena) tenuistriata PÉREZ, 1895.

Andrena pilosella DESTEFANI, 1889.

167. Andrena (Plastandrena) tibialis (KIRBY, 1802).

Andrena cypricola MAVROMOUSTAKI, 1952.

168. Andrena (Hoplandrena) trimmerana (KIRBY, 1802).

Andrena spinigera (KIRBY, 1802).

171. *Andrena (Melandrena) vaga* PANZER, 1799.
Andrena nitidiventris BLANCHARD, 1850.
173. *Andrena (Andrena) varians* (KIRBY, 1802).
Andrena mesoxantha IMHOFF, 1834.
176. *Andrena (Graecandrena) verticalis* PÉREZ, 1895.
Andrena catania STRAND, 1921.
178. *Andrena (Truncandrena) villipes* PÉREZ, 1895.
Espèce notée sous le nom d'*Andrena squalida* PÉREZ, 1903 dans le travail de RASMONT *et al.* (1995).
179. *Andrena (Poecilandrena) viridescens* VIREECK, 1916.
Andrena cyanescens NYLANDER, 1852 *nec* HALIDAY, 1836.
181. *Andrena (Euandrena) vulpecula* KRIECHBAUMER, 1873.
Andrena obscurella PÉREZ, 1903.

Sous-famille **Panurginae** LEACH, 1815.

Genre **Camptopoeum** SPINOLA, 1843.

1. *Camptopoeum (Camptopoeum) nasutum* (SPINOLA, 1838).
Camptopoeum ligusticus GRIBODO, 1896.

Genre **Panurgus** PANZER, 1806.

3. *Panurgus (Pachycephalopanurgus) canescens* LATREILLE, 1811.
Panurgus hispanicus (GIRAUD, 1861) – *Panurgus soikai* PITTONI, 1950.
4. *Panurgus (Panurgus) cephalotes* LATREILLE, 1811.
Panurgus arctos ERICHSON, 1835.

Famille **Apidae** LATREILLE, 1802.

Sous-famille **Apinae** LATREILLE, 1802.

Genre **Amegilla** FRIESE, 1897.

1. *Amegilla (Zebamegilla) albigena* (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Anthophora binotata (LEPELETIER, 1841) – *Amegilla nana* (RADOSZKOWSKI, 1869) – *Podalirius pyramidalis* (KIRBY, 1900) – *Amegilla fasciata* ORTIZ-SÁNCHEZ & JIMENEZ, 1991 – ? *Anthophora graeca* ALFKEN, 1942.
2. *Amegilla (Micramegilla) fasciata* (FABRICIUS, 1775).
Anthophora candens (PÉREZ, 1879), *nec* SMITH, 1879 – *Anthophora candida* Pérez, 1879 – *Amegilla andresi*, ORTIZ-SÁNCHEZ & JIMENEZ, 1991.
3. *Amegilla (Amegilla) garrula* (ROSSI, 1790).
Anthophora bombylans MOCSÁRY, 1879.
6. *Amegilla (Zebamegilla) savignyi* (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Anthophora magnilabris FEDTSCHENKO, 1875.

Genre **Anthophora** LATREILLE, 1803.

1. *Anthophora (Pyganthophora) aestivalis* (PANZER, 1801).
Anthophora intermedia LEPELETIER, 1841.
2. *Anthophora (Lophanthophora) affinis* BRULLÉ, 1832.
Anthophora biciliata LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthophora liturata* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthophora asiatica* var. *lusitanica* (FRIESE, 1919).
3. *Anthophora (Lophanthophora) agama* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1869.
Anthophora caucasica RADOSZKOWSKI, 1874 – *Anthophora kessleri* FEDCHENKO, 1875.
4. *Anthophora (Pyganthophora) atriceps* PÉREZ, 1879.
Anthophora thomsonii (SAUNDERS, 1882).
6. *Anthophora (Paramegilla) balneorum* LEPELETIER, 1841.
Anthophora obesa GIRAUD, 1863.
7. *Anthophora (Heliophila) bimaculata* (PANZER, 1798).
Apis rotundata PANZER, 1798 – *Anthophora saropoda* LAMARCK, 1817 – *Anthophora squalida* LEPELETIER, 1841.
9. *Anthophora (Anthophora) canescens* BRULLÉ, 1832.
Anthophora subterranea GERMAR, 1826 – *Anthophora nigrocincta* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthophora lanata* (KLUG, 1845) – *Anthophora dalmatiensis* STRAND, 1916 – *Anthophora laticincta* DOURS, 1869 – *Anthophora procera* COSTA, 1883 – *Anthophora senescens* subsp. *canescens* DOURS, 1869 – *Anthophora venerabilis* COCKERELL, 1911.
10. *Anthophora (Petalosternon) crassipes* LEPELETIER, 1841.
Anthophora quadristrigata DOURS, 1869 – *Anthophora denticrus* Morawitz, 1872 – *Anthophora perplexa* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1884.
11. *Anthophora (Anthophora) crinipes* SMITH, 1854.
Anthophora salviae (PANZER, 1805) – *Anthophora ephippium* LEPELETIER, 1841.
13. *Anthophora (Caranthophora) dufourii* LEPELETIER, 1841.
Anthophora tecta SMITH, 1854 – *Anthophora dives* DOURS, 1869.
14. *Anthophora (Paramegilla) femorata* (OLIVIER, 1789).
Apis femorata OLIVIER, 1789.

15. *Anthophora (Anthophora) fulvitaris* BRULLÉ, 1832.
Anthophora personata IMHOFF & LABRAM, 1838.
16. *Anthophora (Heliophila) fulvodimidiata* DOURS, 1869.
Anthophora nigripes PÉREZ, 1879.
17. *Anthophora (Clisodon) furcata* (PANZER, 1798).
Apis dumetorum PANZER, 1798.
18. *Anthophora (Paramegilla) gallica* DALLA TORRE & FRIESE, 1895.
Anthophora quadricolor gallica DALLA TORRE & FRIESE, 1895 – *Amegilla gallica* (DALLA TORRE & FRIESE, 1895).
19. *Anthophora (Paramegilla) larvata* GIRAUD, 1863.
Anthophora croceipes MORAWITZ, 1876.
23. *Anthophora (Melea) plagiata* (ILLIGER, 1806).
Apis parietina FABRICIUS, 1793 *nec* GEOFFROY – *Megilla plagiata* ILLIGER, 1806 – *Anthophora mlokosewitszi* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1884 – *Anthophora nigripes* MORAWITZ, 1887 – *Anthophora simplex* (FRIESE, 1897).
24. *Anthophora (Anthophora) plumipes* (PALLAS, 1772).
Anthophora acervorum (LINNAEUS, 1758) – *Andrena hirsuta* FABRICIUS, 1787 – *Apis rufipes* CHRIST, 1791 – *Apis palmipes* ROSSI, 1792 – *Anthophora squalens* DOURS, 1869 var. *niger* (FRIESE, 1806) – *Apis pilipes* FABRICIUS, 1775.
26. *Anthophora (Caranthophora) pubescens* (FABRICIUS, 1781).
Anthophora flabellifera LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthophora flabellipes* LICHTENSTEIN, 1871 – *Anthophora flabellifera* LEPELETIER, 1841.
28. *Anthophora (Dasymegilla) quadrimaculata* (PANZER, 1798).
Apis vulpina PANZER, 1798 – *Apis subglobosa* KIRBY, 1802 – *Anthophora mixta* Lepeletier, 1841 – *Anthophora vara* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthophora segusina* GRIBODO, 1873 – *Anthophora vulpina* (PANZER, 1798) – *Apis quadrimaculata* PANZER, 1798
29. *Anthophora (Pyganthophora) retusa* (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Apis retusa LINNAEUS, 1758 – *Anthophora retusa* var. *meridionalis* PÉREZ, 1879.
30. *Anthophora (Lophanthophora) robusta* (KLUG, 1845).
Anthophora nigromaculata LUCAS, 1846 – *Anthophora oxygona* DOURS, 1869 – *Anthophora oxygona* DOURS, 1869.
32. *Anthophora (Pyganthophora) sichelii* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1869.
Anthophora dimidiozonata DOURS, 1846.

Genre **Habropoda** SMITH, 1854.

1. *Habropoda tarsata* (SPINOLA, 1838).
Anthophora passerini SICHEL, 1856 – *Habropoda ezonata* SMITH, 1854.

Genre **Bombus** LATREILLE, 1802.

3. *Bombus (Psithyrus) barbutellus* (KIRBY, 1802).
Bombus maxillosus KLUG, 1817, considéré comme une sous-espèce de *B. barbutellus* par tous les auteurs modernes (RASMONT *et al.*, 2021). Le taxon *italicus* GRÜTTE est considéré comme un synonyme de *maxillosus* KLUG par ces derniers auteurs.
4. *Bombus (Psithyrus) bohemicus* SEIDL, 1838.
Psithyrus distinctus PÉREZ, 1884.
7. *Bombus (Bombus) confusus* SCHENCK, 1861.
Bombus paradoxus DALLA TORRE, 1882
8. *Bombus (Bombus) cryptarum* (FABRICIUS, 1775).
Bombus lucocryptarum (BALL, 1914) – *Bombus cryptarum reinigianus* RASMONT, 1983.
11. *Bombus (Psithyrus) flavidus* EVERS-MANN, 1852.
Bombus flavidus lutescens (PÉREZ, 1890) – *Bombus flavidus alpium* (RICHARDS, 1928)
13. *Bombus (Megabombus) hortorum* (LINNAEUS, 1760).
Bombus hispanicus PITTONI, 1938 *nec* FRIESE, 1911 – *Megabombus asturiensis* RASMONT, 1983, considéré comme une sous-espèce des Pyrénées et de Péninsule ibérique par RASMONT *et al.* (2021).
14. *Bombus (Thoracobombus) humilis* ILLIGER, 1806.
Bombus solstitialis PANZER, 1805 – *Bombus helferanus* SEIDL, 1837 – *Bombus variabilis* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1878.
17. *Bombus (Pyrobombus) jonellus* (KIRBY, 1802).
Bombus scrimshiranus (KIRBY, 1802).
18. *Bombus (Thoracobombus) laesus* MORAWITZ, 1875.
Bombus mocsaryi KRIECHBAUMER, 1877, ce taxon est considéré comme une sous-espèce de *B. laesus* par BRASERO *et al.* (2021) et RASMONT *et al.* (2021).
21. *Bombus (Bombus) magnus* VOGT, 1911.
Bombus flavoscutellaris TRAUTMANN & TRAUTMANN, 1915 – *Bombus latocinctus* KRÜGER, 1939 – *Bombus luteostriatus* KRÜGER, 1954.
22. *Bombus (Alpigenobombus) mstrucatus* GERSTÄCKER, 1869
Espèce notée sous le nom de *Bombus wurflenii* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1859 dans le travail de RASMONT *et al.* (1995). L'usage de *B. wurflenii* est aujourd'hui restreint aux populations asiatiques (WILLIAMS *et al.*, 2023).

- 25. *Bombus (Pyrobombus) monticola*** SMITH, 1849.
Bombus lapponicus aut. nec FABRICIUS, 1793 – *Bombus lapponicus* DELMAS, 1976.
- 27. *Bombus (Thoracobombus) muscorum*** (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Bombus bannitus (POPOV, 1930), considéré comme une sous-espèce de *B. muscorum* par RASMONT et al. (2021).
- 29. *Bombus (Thoracobombus) pascuorum*** (SCOPOLI, 1763).
Bombus agrorum (FABRICIUS, 1787).
- 30. *Bombus (Thoracobombus) pomorum*** (PANZER, 1805).
Bombus lefebvrei LEPELETIER, 1935 nec auct.
- 34. *Bombus (Bombus) renardi*** RADOSZKOWSKI, 1884.
Bombus lucorum renardi RADOSZKOWSKI, 1884.
- 35. *Bombus (Thoracobombus) ruderarius*** (MÜLLER, 1776).
Apis derhamellus KIRBY, 1802 – *Apis rajellus* KIRBY, 1802 – *Bombus montanus* LEPELETIER, 1836.
- 36. *Bombus (Megabombus) ruderatus*** (FABRICIUS, 1775).
Bombus corsicus SCHULTHESS-RECHBERG, 1886 – *B. hortorum jonghei* RASMONT, 1982 – *Apis autumnalis* FABRICIUS, 1785 – *B. ruderatus autumnalis* (FABRICIUS, 1785) – *B. ruderatus eurynotus* DALLA TORRE, 1882.
- 44. *Bombus (Psithyrus) vestalis*** (GEOFFROY IN FOURCROY, 1785).
Psithyrus perezii SCHULTHESS-RECHBERG, 1886, considéré comme une sous-espèce de *B. vestalis* par RASMONT et al. (2021).
- 45. *Bombus (Thoracobombus) veteranus*** (FABRICIUS, 1793).
Bombus arenicola (THOMSON, 1872).
- 46. *Bombus (Bombus) xanthopus*** KRIECHBAUMER, 1870.
Bombus terrestris xanthopus KRIECHBAUMER, 1870.

Genre *Eucera* SCOPOLI, 1770.

- 4. *Eucera (Eucera) cineraria*** EVERS-MANN, 1852.
Eucera cinerea LEPELETIER, 1841 (*nomen nudum*) – *Eucera concinna* GRIBODO, 1973.
- 5. *Eucera (Eucera) clypeata*** ERICHSON, 1835.
Eucera similis LEPELETIER 1841 – *Eucera fasciatella* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Eucera punctilabris* LEPELETIER 1841 – *Eucera coactata* EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Eucera medusa* NURSE, 1904.
- 8. *Eucera (Eucera) elongatula*** VACHAL, 1907.
Eucera trivittata FRIESE, 1896.
- 13. *Eucera (Eucera) longicornis*** (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Eucera tuberculata (FABRICIUS, 1793) – *Eucera linguaria* LEPELETIER 1841 – *Eucera subrufa* LEPELETIER 1841 – *Eucera difficilis* PÉREZ, 1879 – *Eucera attricolis* FRIESE, 1922 – *Eucera hispaliensis* PÉREZ, 1902.
- 15. *Eucera (Eucera) nigrescens*** PÉREZ, 1879.
Eucera longicornis LATREILLE, 1802 nec (LINNAEUS, 1758) – *Eucera longicornis* var. *cincta* FRIESE 1895 – *Eucera longicornis* var. *immaculata* FRIESE, 1895.
- 17. *Eucera (Eucera) nigrilabris*** LEPELETIER, 1841.
Eucera terminalis SMITH, 1879.
- 20. *Eucera (Eucera) pollinosa*** SMITH, 1854.
Eucera chrysopyga PÉREZ, 1879 – *Eucera distincta* LEPELETIER, 1841.
- 21. *Eucera (Eucera) proxima*** MORAWITZ, 1875.
Eucera graeca RADOSZKOWSKI, 1876 – *Eucera nitidiventris* MOCSÁRY, 1879 – *Eucera bipartita* PÉREZ, 1910.
- 23. *Eucera (Synhalonia) rufa*** (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Espèce en partie notée sous le nom d'*Eucera alternans* (BRULLÉ, 1832) dans le travail de RASMONT et al. (1995).
- 25. *Eucera (Eucera) taurica*** MORAWITZ, 1871.
Eucera spectabilis MOCSÁRY, 1879 – *Eucera asiatica* ALFKEN, 1936 – *Eucera subfasciata* LEPELETIER 1841.
- 26. *Eucera (Synhalonia) tricincta*** ERICHSON, 1835.
Eucera cressa TKALCÚ 1984 – *Tetralonia mavromoustakisi* TKALCÚ 1984.

Genre *Tetralonia* SPINOLA, 1838.

- 2. *Tetralonia dentata*** (KLUG, 1835).
Macrocera tricincta LEPELETIER 1841.
- 3. *Tetralonia fulvescens*** (GIRAUD, 1863).
Macrocera dufourii PÉREZ, 1879 – *Tetralonia acutangula* MORAWITZ, 1878.
- 4. *Tetralonia graja*** (EVERSMANN, 1852).
Eucera ruficornis PÉREZ 1879.
- 6. *Tetralonia julliani*** (PÉREZ, 1879).
Tetralonia biroii (MOCSÁRY, 1879).
- 7. *Tetralonia malvae*** (ROSSI, 1790).
Tetralonia macroglossa Illiger, 1806 – *Macrocera albida* LEPELETIER 1841.
- 12. *Tetralonia strigata*** (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Espèce en partie notée sous le nom de *Tetralonia antigae* (PÉREZ, 1902) et *Tetralonia subaurata* DOURS, 1873 dans la liste de RASMONT et al. (1995).

Genre *Melecta* LATREILLE, 1802.

- 1. *Melecta (Melecta) aegyptiaca*** RADOSZKOWSKI, 1876.
Melecta lindbergi LIEFTINCK, 1958.
- 2. *Melecta (Melecta) albifrons*** (FORSTER, 1771).
Apis punctata FABRICIUS, 1775 – *Andrena armata* PANZER, 1799.
- 3. *Melecta (Melecta) duodecimmaculata*** (ROSSI, 1790).
Melecta plurinotata BRULLÉ, 1832 – *Melecta quattuordecimpunctata* FISCHER-WALDHEIM, 1843 – *Melecta baeri* ALFKEN, 1935 – *Melecta soederbomi* ALFKEN, 1936.
- 6. *Melecta (Melecta) italica*** RADOSZKOWSKI, 1876.
Melecta quadripunctata RADOSZKOWSKI, 1893 – *Melecta acutivalvis* ALFKEN, 1914 – *Melecta crassicornis* FRIESE, 1925.

Genre *Thyreus* PANZER, 1806.

- 1. *Thyreus affinis*** (MORAWITZ, 1874).
Crocica affinis aff. *villosa* MEYER, 1921.
- 4. *Thyreus histrionicus*** (ILLIGER, 1806).
Crocica major MORAWITZ, 1875 – *Crocica divisa* PÉREZ, 1905 – *Crocica truncata* var. *alboscuteolata* MEYER, 1921 – *Crocica dimidiatipunctata* ALFKEN, 1927 – *Crocica rimosiscutum* ALFKEN, 1927.
- 5. *Thyreus orbatus*** (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Crocica scutellaris auct.
- 7. *Thyreus ramosus*** (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Crocica rufa RADOSZKOWSKI, 1886 – *Crocica ramosa* var. *albiciliata* MEYER, 1921 – *Crocica circulata* ALFKEN, 1927.
- 8. *Thyreus truncatus*** (PÉREZ, 1883).
Crocica ramosa var. *mucoarea* FRIESE, 1925 – *Crocica nadigi* ALFKEN, 1933 – *Crocica curviscutum* ALFKEN, 1934.

Sous-famille *Nomadinae* LATREILLE, 1802.

Genre *Ammobates* LATREILLE, 1809.

- 3. *Ammobates (Ammobates) punctatus*** (FABRICIUS, 1804).
Epeolus kirbiensis LATREILLE, 1805 – *Ammobates dufourii* LATREILLE, 1809 – *Ammobates bicolor* LEPELETIER, 1825.

Genre *Ammobatoides* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1867.

- 1. *Ammobatoides scriptus*** (GERSTÄCKER, 1869).
Phiarus melectoides (SMITH, 1854).

Genre *Biastes* PANZER, 1806.

- 1. *Biastes (Biastes) brevicornis*** (PANZER, 1798).
Pasites unicolor JURINE, 1807 – *Pasites atra* SPINOLA, 1808 – *Nomada schottii* FABRICIUS, 1804.
- 2. *Biastes (Biastes) emarginatus*** (SCHENCK, 1853).
Phileremus nasutus GERSTÄCKER, 1869.

Genre *Epeolus* LATREILLE, 1802.

- 1. *Epeolus alpinus*** FRIESE, 1893.
Epeolus glacialis ALFKEN, 1913 – *Epeolus alpinus* BISCHOFF, 1930 – *Epeolus montanus* BISCHOFF, 1930 – *Epeolus pilosus* BISCHOFF, 1930.
- 3. *Epeolus cruciger*** (PANZER, 1799).
Epeolus variegatus auct. nec LINNAEUS, 1758 – *Epeolus rufipes* THOMSON, 1870.
- 4. *Epeolus fallax*** MORAWITZ, 1872.
Epeolus giannellii GRIBODO, 1894 – *Epeolus speculifer* PÉREZ, 1895.
- 6. *Epeolus julliani*** PÉREZ, 1884.
Epeolus transitorius sensu BOGUSH & HADRAVA, 2018, nec EVERS-MANN, 1852 (LE DIVELEC, 2021b).
- 8. *Epeolus tarsalis*** MORAWITZ, 1874.
Epeolus praeustus PÉREZ, 1884.
- 9. *Epeolus variegatus*** (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Epeolus productus THOMSON, 1870.

Genre *Triepeolus* ROBERTSON, 1901.

- 1. *Triepeolus tristis*** (SMITH, 1854).
Epeolus tristis SMITH, 1854.

Genre *Nomada* SCOPOLI, 1770.

- 2. *Nomada alboguttata*** HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839.
Nomada alboguttata var. *liburnica* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada alboguttata* var. *suerinensis* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada ochrostoma* ZETTERSTEDT, 1838 nec (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada quinquespinosa* THOMSON, 1870.
- 3. *Nomada argentata*** HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839.
Nomada atrata SMITH, 1846 – *Nomada brevicornis* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.

4. **Nomada armata** HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839.
Nomada rostrata LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Nomada compta* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Nomada lanceolata* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Nomada kirbyella* STEPHENS, 1846 – *Nomada cincticornis* NYLANDER, 1848.
5. **Nomada atroscutellaris** STRAND, 1921.
Nomada furva var. *atroscutellaris* STRAND, 1921.
6. **Nomada baccata** SMITH, 1844.
Nomada laeta THOMSON, 1870.
7. **Nomada barcelonensis** COCKERELL, 1917.
Nomada excellens PÉREZ, 1913.
8. **Nomada basalis** HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839.
Nomada flavomaculata LUCAS, 1847; DUSMET, 1913 – *Nomada regalis* MORAWITZ, 1870 – *Nomada regalis* var. *inderskiana* LOZIŃSKI, 1922 – *Nomada andalusica* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada astarte* PÉREZ, 1895 – *Nomada bispotta* EVERS-MANN, 1852 nec SCHILLING, 1849 – *Nomada emendata* SCHULZ, 1906 – *Nomada flavospotta* LUCAS, 1849 – *Nomada flavospotta* var. *carnea* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada grossa* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada rubra* SMITH, 1849 – *Nomada tricolor* BRULLÉ, 1832 – *Nomada tripunctata* MORAWITZ, 1872.
9. **Nomada beaumonti** SCHWARZ, 1967.
Nomada serricornis PÉREZ, 1884.
10. **Nomada bifasciata** OLIVIER, 1811.
Nomada pusilla PÉREZ, 1884 – *Nomada planiscuta* SAUNDERS, 1908 – *Nomada lepeletieri* PÉREZ, 1884 – *Nomada navasi* DUSMET, 1913.
11. **Nomada bispinosa** MOCSÁRY, 1883.
Nomada excisa PÉREZ, 1890.
12. **Nomada blepharipes** SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
Nomada helvetica SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada erythrocephala* auct. nec MORAWITZ, 1871.
13. **Nomada bluethgeni** STÖCKHERT, 1943.
Nomada blüthgeni STÖCKHERT, 1943.
14. **Nomada carnifex** MOCSÁRY, 1883.
Nomada lituripes PÉREZ, 1902 – *Nomada tridentilabris* SCHWARZ, 1963.
15. **Nomada castellana** DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1913.
Nomada baeri STÖCKHERT, 1930.
16. **Nomada concolor** SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
Nomada quadridens PÉREZ, 1884.
17. **Nomada conjungens** HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839.
Nomada dallatorreana SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada bipuntis* PÉREZ, 1902.
18. **Nomada distinguenda** MORAWITZ, 1874.
Nomada rugithorax PÉREZ, 1902.
19. **Nomada duplex** SMITH, 1854.
Nomada fucata melanoscapa GRIBODO, 1894 – *Nomada fucata nigroflavida* GRIBODO, 1894 – *Nomada cirtana* PÉREZ, 1895 – *Nomada sardiniensis* FRIESE, 1921.
20. **Nomada errans** LEPELETIER, 1841.
Nomada errans var. *korleviciana* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada errans* var. *sibirica* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada transsylvanica* ENDRE, 1927.
21. **Nomada fabriciana** (LINNAEUS, 1767).
Nomada germanica PANZER, 1799 – *Nomada quadrinotata* (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada fabriciella* (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada nigricornis* OLIVIER, 1811 – *Nomada nigrita* SCHENCK, 1859 nec (PÉREZ, 1895) – *Nomada fabriciana* var. *aestivalis* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada fabriciana* var. *ruficrus* Stoeckhert, 1930.
22. **Nomada femoralis** MORAWITZ, 1869.
Nomada dentipes RUDOW, 1879 – *Nomada femoralis* var. *flavopunctata* FRIESE, 1921.
23. **Nomada fenestrata** LEPELETIER, 1841.
Nomada faventiana PÉREZ, 1902 – *Nomada cebalosi* DUSMET, 1915 – *Nomada vicarioi* DUSMET, 1915 – *Nomada affinis* DUSMET, 1932 nec (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839).
24. **Nomada ferruginata** (LINNAEUS, 1767).
Nomada xanthostica (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada lateralis* (PANZER, 1804) – *Nomada brigmaniana* SMITH, 1876 – *Nomada lateralis* var. *blancoburgensis* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada lateralis* var. *megapolitana* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
25. **Nomada flava** PANZER, 1798.
Nomada intermedia IMHOFF, 1834 – *Nomada proteus* LEPELETIER, 1841.
26. **Nomada flavoguttata** (KIRBY, 1802).
Nomada rufocincta (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada minuta* FABRICIUS, 1805 – *Nomada nana* SCHENCK, 1874 – *Nomada pygmaea* SCHENCK, 1874 nec CRESSON, 1863 – *Nomada flavoguttata* var. *serotina* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada flavoguttata* var. *hoepfneri* ALFKEN, 1898 – *Nomada alfkeni* COCKERELL, 1907 nec GAUNITZ, 1935 nec NOSKIEWICZ, 1939).
27. **Nomada flavopicta** (KIRBY, 1802).
Nomada jacobaeae var. *albopicta* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada jacobaeae* var. *miranda* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada sericea* DUFUR, 1841 – *Nomada jasnitskii* COCKERELL, 1928.
28. **Nomada fucata** PANZER, 1798.
Nomada varia PANZER, 1798 – *Nomada fucata* var. *taeniata* GRIBODO, 1894 – *Nomada fucata* var. *iberica* DALLA TORRE & FRIESE, 1894 – *Nomada fucata* var. *pretiosa* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada fucata* var. *flavescens* FRIESE, 1921 nec *pampicola* var. *flavescens* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada fucata* var. *caucasica* LOZIŃSKI, 1922.
29. **Nomada fulvicornis** FABRICIUS, 1793.
Nomada lineola PANZER, 1798 – *Nomada capreae* (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada cornigera* (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada sexcincta* (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada ventralis* Imhoff, 1834 – *Nomada schmiedeknechti* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada belikovii* COCKERELL, 1928.
30. **Nomada fuscicornis** NYLANDER, 1848.
Nomada megacephala SCHENCK, 1874.
31. **Nomada glaucopsis** PÉREZ, 1890.
Nomada pusilla LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Nomada ferroviaria* DUSMET, 1913.
32. **Nomada goodeniana** (KIRBY, 1802).
Nomada alternata (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada integra* IMHOFF, 1834 nec BRULLÉ, 1832 nec ROBERTSON, 1893 – *Nomada cincta* HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839 nec (ROSSI, 1792) nec LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Nomada batava* VOLLENHOVEN, 1858 – *Nomada succincta* var. *lineolata* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada scheviakovii* (COCKERELL, 1928) – *Nomada goodeniana* ssp. *danuvia* PITTIONI, 1951.
33. **Nomada gribodoi** SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
Nomada basalis PÉREZ, 1895 (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839 – *Nomada dispar* PÉREZ, 1895 – *Nomada elegans* MOCSÁRY, 1897).
34. **Nomada guttulata** SCHENCK, 1861.
Nomada rufilabris THOMSON, 1870.
35. **Nomada hirtipes** PÉREZ, 1884.
Nomada bucephalae PERKINS, 1917.
36. **Nomada hispanica** DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1913.
Nomada nuptura DUSMET, 1913.
37. **Nomada hungarica** DALLA TORRE & FRIESE, 1894.
Nomada scita SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada lagrecai* NOBILE, 1990.
38. **Nomada illustris** SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
Nomada dusmetella PÉREZ, 1913.
39. **Nomada integra** BRULLÉ, 1832.
Nomada ferruginata auct. nec (LINNAEUS, 1767) – *Nomada stigma* auct. nec (LINNAEUS, 1767) – *Nomada germanica* FABRICIUS, 1805 nec (PANZER, 1799) – *Nomada ferruginata* var. *cinctiventris* FRIESE, 1921.
40. **Nomada italica** DALLA TORRE & FRIESE, 1894.
Nomada festiva SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
41. **Nomada jaramensis** DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1913.
Nomada jaramense DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1913.
42. **Nomada kohli** SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
Nomada hipponensis SAUNDERS, 1908.
43. **Nomada kriesteni** SCHWARZ & GUSENLEITNER, 2013.
Nomada longipalpis SCHWARZ & SMIT, 2020.
44. **Nomada lathburiana** (KIRBY, 1802).
Nomada rufiventris (KIRBY, 1802) – *Nomada consobrina* DUFUR, 1841.
45. **Nomada leucophthalma** (KIRBY, 1802).
Nomada borealis ZETTERSTEDT, 1838 – *Nomada inquilina* SMITH, 1844.
46. **Nomada marshamella** (KIRBY, 1802).
Nomada marshamella var. *dubia* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada marshamella* var. *modesta* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 nec CRESSON, 1863, nec HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839.
47. **Nomada mauritanica** Lepeletier, 1841.
Nomada chrysopyga MORAWITZ, 1871 – *Nomada speciosissima* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada superba* PÉREZ, 1902 nec CRESSON, 1863 – *Nomada sericultorum* SCHULZ, 1906 – *Nomada syriaca* FRIESE, 1921.
48. **Nomada melthoracica** IMHOFF, 1834.
Nomada freygessneri SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
49. **Nomada minuscula** NOSKIEWICZ, 1930.
Nomada sheppardana minuscula NOSKIEWICZ, 1930.
50. **Nomada moeschleri** ALFKEN, 1913.
Nomada bifida var. *moeschleri* ALFKEN, 1913.
51. **Nomada mutabilis** MORAWITZ, 1870.
Nomada antigana PÉREZ, 1876 – *Nomada mutabilis* var. *lucifera* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
52. **Nomada mutica** MORAWITZ, 1872.
Nomada cincta LEPELETIER, 1841 nec ROSSI, 1792, nec HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839 – *Nomada olympica* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.

74. *Nomada nigrovaria* PÉREZ, 1895.
Nomada gerundica PÉREZ, 1913.
75. *Nomada nobilis* HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839.
Nomada aberrans EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Nomada calabra* MORAWITZ, 1872 – *Nomada nobilis* var. *magrettiana* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
76. *Nomada numida* LEPELETIER, 1841.
Nomada manni MORAWITZ, 1877 – *Nomada ferghanica* MORAWITZ, 1875.
78. *Nomada obtusifrons* NYLANDER, 1848.
Nomada mistura SMITH, 1851 – *Nomada roberjeotiana* var. *alpina* MORAWITZ, 1867.
79. *Nomada opaca* ALFKEN, 1913.
Nomada bifida var. *opaca* ALFKEN, 1913.
81. *Nomada panurgina* MORAWITZ, 1869.
Nomada julliani SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada julliani* DALLA TORRE, 1896.
82. *Nomada panzeri* LEPELETIER, 1841.
Nomada diluta PÉREZ, 1884 nec GRIBODO, 1893.
83. *Nomada pectoralis* MORAWITZ, 1877.
Nomada pectoralis var. *atroflava* FRIESE, 1921.
84. *Nomada piccioliana* MAGRETTI, 1883.
Nomada novioregensis PÉREZ, 1902 – *Nomada jurassica* STÖCKERT, 1941.
85. *Nomada pleurosticta* HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839.
Nomada ferruginata var. *major* MORAWITZ, 1872 – *Nomada bicolor* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1876 – *Nomada morawitzi*, PÉREZ, 1884.
86. *Nomada posthuma* BLÜTHGEN, 1949.
Nomada mixtella NOSKIEWICZ, 1959.
87. *Nomada pulchra* ARNOLD, 1888.
Nomada olhae COCKERELL, 1928.
88. *Nomada rhenana* MORAWITZ, 1872.
Nomada rufipes SCHENCK, 1870 nec FABRICIUS, 1793.
89. *Nomada roberjeotiana* PANZER, 1799.
Nomada montana MOCSÁRY, 1894 nec (SCOPOLI, 1763) – *Nomada panzeriana* WALKENEAR, 1802 – *Nomada neglecta* HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839 – *Nomada roberjeotiana tormentillae* ALFKEN, 1901.
92. *Nomada ruficornis* (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Nomada bifida THOMSON, 1872.
93. *Nomada rufipes* FABRICIUS, 1793.
Nomada vaga PANZER, 1798 – *Nomada solidaginis* PANZER, 1799 – *Nomada picta* KIRBY, 1802 – *Nomada rufopicta* KIRBY, 1802 – *Nomada solidaginis* var. *punctulifera* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada solidaginis* var. *minutula* FRIESE, 1921 – *Nomada fenica* ALFKEN, 1924 – *Nomada rufipes nigriventris* ALFKEN, 1926.
94. *Nomada sanguinea* SMITH, 1854.
Nomada laevilabris SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada coelomeria* PÉREZ, 1884 – *Nomada clara* PÉREZ, 1896.
96. *Nomada sexfasciata* PANZER, 1799.
Nomada connexa Kirby, 1802 – *Nomada schaefferella* Kirby, 1802.
97. *Nomada sheppardana* (KIRBY, 1802).
Nomada dalii CURTIS, 1832 – *Nomada microsticta* COCKERELL, 1931.
98. *Nomada signata* JURINE, 1807.
Nomada ruficornis var. *mirabilis* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
99. *Nomada similis* MORAWITZ, 1872.
Nomada nigroantennata SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
100. *Nomada stigma* FABRICIUS, 1804.
Nomada cinnabarina MORAWITZ, 1871 – *Nomada cinnabarina* MORAWITZ, 1872 – *Nomada austriaca* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
101. *Nomada striata* FABRICIUS, 1793.
Nomada hillana KIRBY, 1802 – *Nomada ochrostoma* KIRBY, 1802 nec (ZETTERSTEDT, 1838) – *Nomada vidua* SMITH, 1844 – *Nomada punctiscuta* THOMSON, 1870 – *Nomada simillima* PÉREZ, 1913 – *Nomada dzieduszyckii* NOSKIEWICZ, 1924.
103. *Nomada succincta* PANZER, 1798.
Nomada fulvicornis auct. nec FABRICIUS 1793 – *Nomada succincta* var. *mixta* DALLA TORRE, 1877.
105. *Nomada trapeziformis* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882.
Nomada ruficornis var. *trapeziformis* SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882 – *Nomada ruficornis* var. *auctumnalis* DUCKE, 1900.
106. *Nomada tridentirostris* DOURS, 1873.
Nomada amblystoma PÉREZ, 1884 – *Nomada cyphognatha* PÉREZ, 1884.
109. *Nomada zonata* PANZER, 1798.
Nomada bofillana PÉREZ, 1913 – *Nomada banatica* ZILAH-KISS, 1915.

Sous-famille *Xylocopinae* LATREILLE, 1802.

Genre *Ceratina* LATREILLE, 1802.

2. *Ceratina (Euceratina) chalcites* GERMAR, 1839.
Apis caerulea VILLERS, 1789 – *Megilla chalcites* ILLIGER, 1806 – *Ceratina aenea*

- BRULLÉ 1832 – *Ceratina egregia* GERSTÄCKER, 1896.
3. *Ceratina (Euceratina) chalybea* CHEVRIER, 1872.
Ceratina hungarica MOCSARY, 1879 – *Ceratina callosa algeriensis* FRIESE 1896 – *Ceratina callosa cephalica* COCKERELL, 1931.
4. *Ceratina (Ceratina) cucurbitina* (ROSSI, 1792).
Hylaeus albilabris FABRICIUS, 1793 – *Ceratina decolorans* BRULLÉ, 1832.
5. *Ceratina (Euceratina) cyanea* (KIRBY, 1802).
Ceratina coerulea CHEVRIER, 1872 – *Ceratina chevrieri* TOURNIER, 1976 – *Ceratina cyanea imitatrix* MARKOWSKY, 1938.
8. *Ceratina (Euceratina) gravidula* GERSTÄCKER, 1869.
Ceratina nigroaenea GERSTÄCKER, 1869.
11. *Ceratina (Dalyatina) parvula* SMITH, 1854.
Ceratina pygmaea LICHTENSTEIN, 1872 – *Ceratina scintilla* COCKERELL, 1931.

Genre *Xylocopa* LATREILLE, 1802.

1. *Xylocopa (Rhysoxylocopa) cantabrita* LEPELETIER, 1841.
Xylocopa sinuatifrons SPINOLA, 1843 – *Xylocopa cantabrica* GERSTÄCKER, 1872.
2. *Xylocopa (Copolylocopa) iris* (CHRIST, 1791).
Xylocopa canuta RONDANI, 1874 – *Xylocopa cyanescens* BRULLÉ, 1832 – *Xylocopa minuta* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Xylocopa taurica* ERICHSON, 1841 – *Xylocopa uclesiensis* PÉREZ, 1901.
4. *Xylocopa (Xylocopa) valga* GERSTÄCKER, 1872.
Xylocopa convexa SMITH, 1878.

Famille *Colletidae* LEPELETIER, 1841.

Sous-famille *Colletinae* LEPELETIER, 1841.

Genre *Colletes* LATREILLE, 1802.

3. *Colletes albomaculatus* (LUCAS, 1849).
Colletes spectabilis MORAWITZ, 1868 – *Colletes niveofasciatus* DOURS, 1872.
5. *Colletes canescens* SMITH, 1853.
Colletes nadigi NOSKIEWICZ, 1933 – *Colletes tarsalis* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936.
6. *Colletes collaris* DOURS, 1872.
Colletes incerta RADOSZKOWSKI, 1891 – *Colletes frigidus* PÉREZ, 1903 – *Andrena riukiensis* MATSUMURA, 1926.
7. *Colletes cunicularius* (LINNAEUS, 1760).
Colletes cinerea (FOURCROY, 1785) – *Colletes hirtus* LEPELETIER, 1825 – *Colletes pilosus* SPINOLA, 1838 – *Colletes cunicularius infuscatus* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936 – *Colletes cunicularius celticus* O'TOOLE, 1974 – *Colletes cunicularius tauricus* WARNCKE, 1978 – *Colletes cunicularius khasanensis* OSYTSYHNJUK, 1995.
8. *Colletes daviesanus* SMITH, 1846.
Apis canus GMELIN, 1790 – *Colletes daviesanus signatus* VERHOEFF, 1890.
9. *Colletes dusmeti* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936.
Colletes restingensis NOSKIEWICZ, 1936 – *Colletes caspicus dusmeti* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936.
10. *Colletes eous* MORICE, 1904.
Colletes cecrops MORICE, 1904 – *Colletes porosicus* STRAND, 1921 – *Colletes illyricus* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936 – *Colletes dimidiatus eous* MORICE, 1904.
11. *Colletes floralis* EVERS-MANN, 1852.
Colletes alpinus MORAWITZ, 1872 – *Colletes montanus* MORAWITZ, 1876 – *Colletes suecica* AUREVILLIUS, 1903 – *Colletes kudiensis* COCKERELL, 1924 – *Colletes yasumatsui* HIRASHIMA & IKUDOME, 1989.
12. *Colletes fodiens* (FOURCROY, 1785).
Apis fosorius RAZOUMOWSKY, 1789 – *Apis pallidicincta* KIRBY, 1802 – *Colletes kirgisica* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1867 – *Colletes fodiens hispanicus* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936.
13. *Colletes foveolaris* PÉREZ, 1903.
Colletes sericeus PÉREZ, 1903 – *Colletes phalericus* MORICE, 1904.
14. *Colletes gallicus* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1891.
Colletes emarginatus PÉREZ, 1903 – *Colletes elongata* FREY-GESSNER, 1903 – *Colletes carinatus gallicus* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1891.
15. *Colletes halophilus* VERHOEFF, 1944.
Apis invictus HARRIS, 1776 – *Colletes succinctus halophilus* VERHOEFF, 1944 – *Colletes succinctus invictus* (HARRIS, 1776).
17. *Colletes hylaeiformis* EVERS-MANN, 1852.
Colletes chobauti PÉREZ, 1903.
19. *Colletes ligatus* ERICHSON, 1835.
Colletes acanthopygus DOURS, 1872 – *Colletes hylaeiformis ligatus* ERICHSON, 1835.
20. *Colletes maidli* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936.
Colletes lebedewi NOSKIEWICZ, 1936 – *Colletes caspicus lebedewi* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936 – *Colletes caspicus maidli* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936.
21. *Colletes marginatus* SMITH, 1846.
Colletes thomsoni ALFKEN, 1899.

22. *Colletes mlokoszewiczi* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1891.
Colletes brevicornis PÉREZ, 1903 nec ROBERTSON, 1897 – *Colletes brachycerus* SWENK, 1906.
23. *Colletes nigricans* GISTEL, 1857.
Colletes alluaudi COCKERELL, 1931 – *Colletes flavescens* NOSKIEWICZ, 1936 – *Colletes siciliensis* NOSKIEWICZ, 1959 – *Colletes dimidiatus tyrrhenicus* WARNCKE, 1978 – *Colletes dimidiatus nigricans* GISTEL, 1857.
24. *Colletes pulchellus* PÉREZ, 1903.
Colletes ibericus NOSKIEWICZ 1936.
26. *Colletes similis* SCHENCK, 1853.
Colletes picistigma THOMSON, 1872.
27. *Colletes succinctus* (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Apis glutinans CUVIER, 1798 – *Apis calendarum* PANZER, 1806 – *Colletes balteatus* NYLANDER, 1852 – *Andrena xanthothorax* EVERS-MANN, 1852.

Sous-famille *Hylaeinae* VIERECK, 1916.

Genre *Hylaeus* FABRICIUS, 1793.

3. *Hylaeus (Lambdopsis) annularis* (KIRBY, 1802).
Hylaeus spilotus FÖRSTER, 1871.
16. *Hylaeus (Lambdopsis) dilatatus* (KIRBY, 1802).
Hylaeus annularis auct. nec (KIRBY, 1802) – *Prosopis cervicornis* COSTA, 1858.
26. *Hylaeus (Prosopis) incongruus* FÖRSTER, 1871.
Prosopis genalis THOMSON 1872.
36. *Hylaeus (Hylaeus) paulus* BRIDWELL, 1919.
Hylaeus lepidulus COCKERELL, 1924.
40. *Hylaeus (Prosopis) pictus* (SMITH, 1853).
Hylaeus bicarinatus (PÉREZ, 1903).
41. *Hylaeus (Dentigera) pilosulus* (PÉREZ, 1903).
Hylaeus conformis auct. nec FÖRSTER, 1871.
42. *Hylaeus (Spatulariella) punctatus* (BRULLÉ, 1832).
Hylaeus subquadratus FÖRSTER, 1871.
44. *Hylaeus (Prosopis) purpurissatus* (VACHAL, 1895).
Hylaeus stigmorhinus (PÉREZ, 1895).
47. *Hylaeus (Dentigera) rubicola* SAUNDERS, 1850.
Prosopis decolorata PÉREZ, 1903 – *Prosopis rectanguliceps* ALFKEN, 1928.
48. *Hylaeus (Prosopis) signatus* (PANZER, 1798).
Hylaeus bipunctatus (FABRICIUS, 1798).
50. *Hylaeus (Paraprosopis) soror* (PÉREZ, 1903).
Prosopis dubitata ALFKEN, 1904.
53. *Hylaeus (Paraprosopis) taeniolatus* FÖRSTER, 1871.
Hylaeus diplonymus auct. nec (SCHULZ, 1906).

Famille *Halictidae* THOMSON, 1869.

Sous-famille *Halictinae* THOMSON, 1869.

Genre *Halictus* LATREILLE, 1804.

4. *Halictus (Halictus) brunnescens* (EVERSMANN, 1852).
Hylaeus brunnescens EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Halictus aegyptiacus* FRIESE, 1916.
7. *Halictus (Monilapis) compressus* (WALCKENAER, 1802).
Halictus eurygnathus BLÜTHGEN, 1931 – *Halictus eurygnathopsis* BLÜTHGEN, 1936 – *Halictus veneticus* EBMER, 1969.
9. *Halictus (Hexataenites) fulvipes* (KLUG, 1817).
Halictus sexcinctellus DOURS, 1872.
11. *Halictus (Monilapis) langobardicus* BLÜTHGEN, 1944.
Halictus tetrazonius var. *nitens* DALLA TORRE, 1877.
12. *Halictus (Tythalictus) maculatus* SMITH, 1848.
Halictus interruptus LEPELETIER, 1841 nec (PANZER, 1798).
15. *Halictus (Halictus) quadricinctus* (FABRICIUS, 1776).
Halictus quadristrigatus LATREILLE, 1805 – *Halictus ecaphosus* WALCKENAER, 1817.
16. *Halictus (Protohalictus) rubicundus* (CHRIST, 1791).
Halictus nidulans WALCKENAER, 1817.
17. *Halictus (Hexataenites) scabiosae* (ROSSI, 1790).
Halictus alternans (FABRICIUS, 1793) – *Halictus zebrus* WALCKENAER, 1817.
18. *Halictus (Hexataenites) sexcinctus* (FABRICIUS, 1775).
Halictus flavipes (FÜESSLY, 1775) (nomen dubium) – *Halictus hortensis* (FOURCOY, 1785).
19. *Halictus (Monilapis) simplex* BLÜTHGEN, 1923.
Halictus ibex WARNCKE, 1973 – *Halictus marchali*, WARNCKE, 1986 (nomen dubium).
- Genre *Lasioglossum* CURTIS, 1833.
1. *Lasioglossum (Dialictus) aeratum* (KIRBY, 1802).
Halictus viridiaeneus BLÜTHGEN, 1832 – *Halictus semiaeneus* BRULLÉ, 1832.
2. *Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) albipes* (FABRICIUS, 1781).
Apis agrestis FOURCROY, 1785 – *Lasioglossum albipes* var. *alpicolus* (BLÜTHGEN, 1920).
3. *Lasioglossum (Leuchalictus) albocinctum* (LUCAS, 1849).
Halictus albomaculatus auct. nec LUCAS, 1846 – *Halictus separandus* FREY-GESSNER, 1903.
6. *Lasioglossum (Dialictus) alpigenum* (DALLA TORRE, 1877).
Halictus alpigenum DALLA TORRE, 1877 – *Halictus subauratus* subsp. *alpigenus* DALLA TORRE, 1877 – *Halictus smeathmanellus* var. *alpigenus* DALLA TORRE, 1877 – *Lasioglossum apostoli* EBMER, 1970.
11. *Lasioglossum (Lasioglossum) bimaculatum* (DOURS, 1872).
Halictus perezi (ALFKEN, 1907).
13. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) brevicorne* (SCHENCK, 1868).
Halictus analis PÉREZ, 1903.
14. *Lasioglossum (Lasioglossum) breviventre* (SCHENCK, 1853).
Halictus chalconotus PÉREZ, 1896.
16. *Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) calceatum* (SCOPOLI, 1763).
Halictus terebrator WALCKENAER, 1817.
19. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) convexusculum* (SCHENCK, 1853).
Halictus puncticollis var. *genevense* FREY-GESSNER, 1903.
20. *Lasioglossum (Dialictus) corsicanum* (BLÜTHGEN, 1931).
Lasioglossum morio corsicanum (BLÜTHGEN, 1931).
26. *Lasioglossum (Leuchalictus) discus* (SMITH, 1853).
Halictus morbillosus KRIECHBAUMER, 1873 – *Lasioglossum pseudomorbillosum* EBMER, 1970.
29. *Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) euboense* (STRAND, 1909).
Halictus kirschbaumi BLÜTHGEN, 1918.
30. *Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) fratellum* (PÉREZ, 1903).
Lasioglossum nigrum auct. nec (VIERECK, 1903).
32. *Lasioglossum (Pygmalictus) glabriusculum* (MORAWITZ, 1872).
Halictus leucopygus PÉREZ, 1903.
33. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) griseolum* (MORAWITZ, 1872).
Lasioglossum misellum (PÉREZ, 1903).
36. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) intermedium* (SCHENCK, 1869).
Lasioglossum melanoproctum (PÉREZ, 1903).
37. *Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) interruptum* (PANZER, 1798).
Lasioglossum geminum (ERICHSON, 1835).
41. *Lasioglossum (Lasioglossum) laterale* (BRULLÉ, 1832).
Halictus ticinensis FREY-GESSNER, 1903.
42. *Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) laticeps* (SCHENCK, 1868).
Hylaeus affinis SCHENCK 1853, nec SMITH 1853.
46. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) limbellum* (MORAWITZ, 1876).
Halictus gibbulus PÉREZ, 1903.
49. *Lasioglossum (Dialictus) littorale* (BLÜTHGEN, 1923).
Halictus littoralis BLÜTHGEN, 1923.
50. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) lucidulum* (SCHENCK, 1861).
Halictus unguinosus PÉREZ, 1903.
51. *Lasioglossum (Leuchalictus) majus* (NYLANDER, 1852).
Halictus lichtensteini PÉREZ, 1903.
54. *Lasioglossum (Biennialaeus) marginatum* (BRULLÉ, 1832).
Halictus fasciatellus SCHENCK, 1869 – *Halictus gribodi* KRIECHBAUMER, 1873.
55. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) marginellum* (SCHENCK, 1853).
Halictus marqueti PÉREZ, 1903.
57. *Lasioglossum (Evylaeus) medinai* (VACHAL, 1895).
Lasioglossum villosulum (chez RASMONT et al., 1995).
61. *Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) minutulum* (SCHENCK, 1853).
Halictus ambiguus SCHENCK, 1861 – *Halictus semipunctulatus* SCHENCK, 1869.
62. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) monstrificum* (MORAWITZ, 1891).
Halictus sabulosus WARNCKE, 1986.
64. *Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) nigripes* (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Halictus vulpinus NYLANDER, 1841 – *Halictus nylanderi* PÉREZ, 1903.
65. *Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) nitidiusculum* (KIRBY, 1802).
Halictus nitidulus PÉREZ, 1903, nec (FABRICIUS, 1804).
66. *Lasioglossum (Dialictus) nitidulum* (FABRICIUS, 1804).
Halictus continentalis (BLÜTHGEN, 1944) ssp. *hammi* (SAUNDERS, 1904).
67. *Lasioglossum (Lasioglossum) pallens* (BRULLÉ, 1832).
Halictus lineolatus LEPELETIER, 1841, nec *Apis lineolata* SCHRANK, 1802 – *Halictus cirrhorzonius* VACHAL, 1895.

- 68. Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) parvulum** (SCHENCK, 1853).
Halictus minutus SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1930.
- 69. Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) pauperatum** (BRULLÉ, 1832).
Halictus breviceps SAUNDERS, 1879 – *Hylaeus pullus* ERICHSON, 1835.
- 77. Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) pygmaeum** (SCHENCK, 1853).
Halictus distinctus SCHENCK, 1868 – *Hylaeus nitidus* SCHENCK, 1853, nec (PANZER, 1798).
- 78. Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) quadrinotatum** (SCHENCK, 1861).
Halictus megacephalus SCHENCK, 1869 – *Halictus sexsignatus* SCHENCK, 1869.
- 85. Lasioglossum (Lasioglossum) sexnotatum** (KIRBY, 1802).
Andrena nitida (PANZER, 1798) nec (MÜLLER, 1776).
- 88. Lasioglossum (Dialictus) soror** (SAUNDERS, 1901).
Halictus atrovirens PÉREZ, 1903.
- 91. Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) subaenescens** (PÉREZ, 1895).
Lasioglossum illyricum EBMER, 1971.
- 92. Lasioglossum (Lasioglossum) subfasciatum** (IMHOFF, 1832).
Halictus rufocinctus NYLANDER, 1852.
- 94. Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) subhirtum** (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Halictus malachuropis COCKERELL, 1937.
- 96. Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) transitorium** (SCHENCK, 1869).
Lasioglossum planulum PÉREZ, 1903.
- 97. Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) tricinatum** (SCHENCK, 1874).
Halictus delmasi PÉREZ, 1903.
- 98. Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) truncaticolle** (MORAWITZ, 1877).
Halictus brevithorax PÉREZ, 1903.
- 100. Lasioglossum (Dialictus) virens** (ERICHSON, 1835).
Halictus simulans (PÉREZ, 1895).
- 101. Lasioglossum (Lasioglossum) xanthopus** (KIRBY, 1802).
Hylaeus densus IMHOFF, 1832.

Genre **Seladonia** ROBERTSON, 1918.

- 3. Seladonia (Seladonia) gemma** (DOURS, 1872).
Halictus cephalicus BLÜTHGEN, 1922.
- 4. Seladonia (Seladonia) gemmella** PAULY, 2015.
Halictus smaragdulus auct. nec VACHAL, 1895 partim 1.
- 6. Seladonia (Pachyceble) leucahenea** (EBMER, 1972).
Halictus fasciatus auct. nec NYLANDER, 1848.
- 9. Seladonia (Seladonia) seladonia** (FABRICIUS, 1794).
Halictus geminatus PÉREZ, 1903.
- 10. Seladonia (Seladonia) smaragdula** (VACHAL, 1895).
Halictus barcelonicus PÉREZ, 1903.
- 11. Seladonia (Seladonia) subaurata** (ROSSI, 1792).
Halictus virescens LEPELETIER, 1841.
- 12. Seladonia (Seladonia) submediterranea** PAULY, 2015.
Halictus smaragdulus auct. nec VACHAL, 1895 partim 2.
- 13. Seladonia (Pachyceble) tumulorum** (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Halictus crocipes (FOURCROY, 1785).
- 14. Seladonia (Vestitohalictus) vestita** (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Halictus tectus RADOSZKOWSKI, 1875 – *Halictus velatus* PÉREZ, 1895.

Genre **Sphecodes** LATREILLE, 1804.

- 1. Sphecodes albilabris** (FABRICIUS, 1793).
Dichroa fuscipennis GERMAR, 1819 – *Sphecodes latreillii* WESMAEL, 1836 – *Sphecodes nigripes* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Sphecodes rugosus* SMITH, 1848 – *Sphecodes nodicornis* GISTEL, 1857 – *Sphecodes fuscipennis* var. *basalis* DALLA TORRE, 1877 – *Sabulicola cirsii* VERHOEFF, 1890 – *Sphecodes grandis* MEYER, 1922.
- 2. Sphecodes alternatus** SMITH, 1853.
Sphecodes punctiventris HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes antigae* TOURNIER, 1901 – *Sphecodes alternatus* ssp. *lindbergi* PITTIONI, 1950.
- 4. Sphecodes crassus** THOMSON, 1870.
Sphecodes variegatus HAGENS, 1874 – *Sphecodes divisus* HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes valesianus* FREY-GESSNER, 1903.
- 8. Sphecodes ephippius** (LINNAEUS, 1767).
Apis minimus HARRIS, 1776 – *Apis rufescens* GEOFFROY in FOURCROY, 1785 – *Apis obscura* GEOFFROY in FOURCROY 1785 – *Apis rufescens* GMELIN in LINNAEUS 1790 – *Apis labiata* FABRICIUS, 1793 – *Melitta divisa* KIRBY, 1802 – *Andrena minuta* FABRICIUS, 1804 – *Sphecodes similis* WESMAEL, 1836 – *Sphecodes zablocki* BLÜTHGEN, 1923.
- 9. Sphecodes ferruginatus** HAGENS, 1882.
Sphecodes rufescens var. *alpestris* FREY-GESSNER, 1903.
- 10. Sphecodes geoffrellus** (KIRBY, 1802).
Sphecodes affinis HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes fasciatus* HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes rimalis* PÉREZ, 1903 – *Sphecodes impunctatus* MEYER, 1922.

- 11. Sphecodes gibbus** (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Apis glabra FÜESSLY, 1775 – *Andrena ferruginea* OLIVIER, 1789 – *Apis gibbosa* CHRIST, 1791 – *Melitta sphecodes* KIRBY, 1802 – *Melitta picea* KIRBY, 1802 – *Andrena austriaca* FABRICIUS, 1804, nec PANZER 1798 – *Dichroa analis* ILLIGER, 1806 – *Sphecodes apicatus* SMITH, 1853 – *Sphecodes nippon* MEYER, 1922 – *Sphecodes castilianus* BLÜTHGEN, 1924.
- 13. Sphecodes intermedius** BLÜTHGEN, 1923.
Sphecodes lactipennis MEYER, 1925.
- 14. Sphecodes longulus** HAGENS, 1882.
Sphecodes longulus var. *epidus* HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes nitidulus* HAGENS, 1882.
- 15. Sphecodes majalis** PÉREZ, 1903.
Sphecodes gracilior PÉREZ, 1903 – *Sphecodes problematicus* SCHULZ, 1906.
- 16. Sphecodes marginatus** HAGENS, 1882.
Sphecodes atratus HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes nigrutilus* HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes nomioides* PESENKO, 1979.
- 17. Sphecodes miniatus** HAGENS, 1882.
Sphecodes dimidiatus HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes murithianus* FREY-GESSNER, 1903 – *Sphecodes pilicornis* MEYER, 1922.
- 18. Sphecodes monilicornis** (KIRBY, 1802).
Sphecodes maculatus LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Sphecodes subquadratus* SMITH, 1845 – *Sphecodes gibbus* var. *ephippium* subvar. *rufipes* SICHEL, 1865, nec SMITH, 1853 – *Sphecodes gibbus* var. *subquadratus* subvar. *dubius* SICHEL, 1865 – *Sphecodes gibbus* var. *subquadratus* subvar. *incertus* SICHEL, 1865 – *Sphecodes gibbus* var. *ephippium* subvar. *nigrescens* SICHEL, 1865 – *Sphecodes gibbus* var. *ephippium* subvar. *testaceipes* SICHEL, 1865 – *Sphecodes ruficrus* DALLA TORRE, 1896, nec ERICHSON, 1835 – *Sphecodes hanuman* NURSE, 1903 – *Sphecodes monilicornis* var. *nigerrima* BLÜTHGEN, 1927 – *Sphecodes caucasicus* MEYER, 1920.
- 19. Sphecodes niger** HAGENS, 1874.
Sphecodes niger var. *holomelaena* BLÜTHGEN, 1949.
- 20. Sphecodes olivieri** Lepeletier & Serville in LATREILLE, 1825.
Sphecodes verticalis von HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes collaris* SPINOLA, 1843 – *Sphecodes hispanicus* var. *abyssinicus* SICHEL, 1865 – *Sphecodes ruficornis* SICHEL, 1865 – *Sphecodes punctulatus* SICHEL, 1865 – *Sphecodes subpunctulatus* SICHEL, 1865 – *Sphecodes rufithorax* MORAWITZ, 1876 – *Sphecodes verticalis* HAGENS, 1882 – *Sphecodes desertus* NURSE, 1903 – *Sphecodes chionospilus* COCKERELL, 1911 – *Sphecodes chionospilus* var. *sanguinatus* COCKERELL, 1911 – *Sphecodes tenuis* MEYER, 1920 – *Sphecodes olivieri* var. *niveatus* MEYER, 1925.
- 21. Sphecodes pellucidus** SMITH, 1845.
Sphecodes pilifrons THOMSON, 1870 – *Sphecodes brevicornis* HAGENS, 1874 – *Sphecodes volatilis* SMITH, 1879 – *Sphecodes pellucidus* var. *algerius* ALFKEN, 1914 – *Sphecodes pellucidus* var. *niveipennis* MEYER, 1925 – *Sphecodes pellucidus* var. *hybridus* BLÜTHGEN, 1925.
- 22. Sphecodes pinguiculus** PÉREZ, 1903.
Sphecodes excellens MEYER, 1922 – *Sphecodes coelebs* BLÜTHGEN, 1923.
- 23. Sphecodes pseudofasciatus** BLÜTHGEN, 1925.
Sphecodes croaticus pseudofasciatus BLÜTHGEN, 1925.
- 24. Sphecodes puncticeps** THOMSON, 1870.
Sphecodes bituberculatus PÉREZ, 1903 – *Sphecodes opacifrons* PÉREZ, 1903 – *Sphecodes puncticeps* var. *cretanus* STRAND, 1921.
- 25. Sphecodes reticulatus** THOMSON, 1870.
Sphecodes distinguendus HAGENS, 1874.
- 27. Sphecodes ruficrus** (ERICHSON, 1835).
Sphecodes hispanicus WESMAEL, 1836 – *Sphecodes rufipes* SMITH, 1853 – *Sphecodes gibbus* var. *tunetanus* GRIBODO, 1894 – *Sphecodes atrohirtus* PÉREZ, 1903 – *Sphecodes rubicundus* ssp. *altsilesiacus* TORKA, 1927.
- 28. Sphecodes rufiventris** (PANZER, 1798).
Sphecodes subovalis SCHENCK, 1853 – *Sphecodes brevis* HAGENS, 1875 – *Sphecodes singularis* MEYER, 1920 – *Sphecodes combinatus* BLÜTHGEN, 1927 – *Sphecodes subovalis* austrinus var. *balkanicus* ERLANDSSON, 1979.
- 29. Sphecodes scabricollis** WESMAEL, 1835.
Sphecodes perversus RITSEMA, 1879.
- 30. Sphecodes schenckii** HAGENS, 1882.
Sphecodes sulcicollis PÉREZ, 1903.

Sous-famille **Nomiinae** ROBERTSON, 1904.

Genre **Nomiapis** COCKERELL, 1919.

- 3. Nomiaapis paulyi** (WOOD & LE DIVELEC, 2022).
Nomia rufiventris auct. nec SPINOLA, 1838 (WOOD & LE DIVELEC, 2022).

Sous-famille **Rophitinae** SCHENCK, 1866.

Genre **Dufourea** LEPELETIER, 1841.

1. **Dufourea dentiventris** (NYLANDER, 1848).
Dufourea dejeani LEPELETIER 1841 (*nomen oblitum*).
2. **Dufourea halictula** (NYLANDER, 1852).
Dufourea minuta auct. partim, nec LEPELETIER 1841.
5. **Dufourea minuta** LEPELETIER, 1841.
Dufourea vulgaris SCHENCK, 1861.

Famille **Megachilidae** LATREILLE, 1802.

Sous-famille **Lithurginae** NEWMAN, 1834.

Genre **Lithurgus** BERTHOLD, 1827.

1. **Lithurgus chrysurus** FONSCOLOMBE, 1834.
Lithurgus analis LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Lithurgus haemorroidalis* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Lithurgus chrysurus* var. *siculus* PÉREZ, 1897.
2. **Lithurgus cornutus** (FABRICIUS, 1787).
Lithurgus nasutus DUFOR, 1849 – *Lithurgus umbraculatus* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Megachile dohrni* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1862 – *Megachile monocerus* EVERS-MANN, 1852.

Sous-famille **Megachilinae** LATREILLE, 1802.

Genre **Aglaopis** CAMERON, 1901.

1. **Aglaopis tridentata** (NYLANDER, 1848).
Dioxoides kuntzei NOSKIEWICZ, 1940.

Genre **Anthidiellum** COCKERELL, 1904.

2. **Anthidiellum strigatum** (PANZER, 1805).
Anthidium contractum LATREILLE, 1809 – *Anthidium frontale* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium scapulare* SCHENCK, 1851 – *Anthidium minusculum* NYLANDER, 1852 – *Anthidium signatum* SCHENCK, 1868 – *Anthidium coronatum* DUFOR, 1853 – *Anthidium decoratum* CHEVRIER, 1872 – *Anthidium strigatum* var. *luteum* FRIESE, 1897 – *Dianthidium leucorhinum* COCKERELL, 1924 – *Anthidiellum pauperulum* COCKERELL, 1928 – *Anthidium strigatum* var. *palaestinense* ALFKEN, 1935 – *Anthidium strigatum judaicum* ALFKEN, 1936 – *Anthidium strigatum humerale* ALFKEN, 1936 – *Anthidium strigatum ibericum* ALFKEN, 1936 – *Anthidiellum strigatum rhodium* TKALCÚ, 2006.

Genre **Anthidium** FABRICIUS, 1804.

1. **Anthidium (Anthidium) cingulatum** LATREILLE, 1809.
Anthidium oraniense LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium dissectum* EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Anthidium imitator* SMITH, 1879 – *Anthidium rufispinum* COSTA, 1883 – *Anthidium manicatum* var. *undulatifasciatum* FRIESE, 1917.
2. **Anthidium (Anthidium) diadema** LATREILLE, 1809.
Anthidium albiventre LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium ornatum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium radoszkowskyi* MOCSÁRY, 1887 – *Anthidium seraxense* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1893 – *Anthidium terminale* homonym MORAWITZ, 1894 – *Anthidium diadema* var. *caucasicum* FRIESE, 1897 – *Anthidium diadema* var. *turcestanicum* FRIESE, 1897 – *Anthidium diadema* var. *obscurum* FRIESE, 1897.
3. **Anthidium (Anthidium) florentinum** (FABRICIUS, 1775).
Anthidium subspinosum KLUG, 1832 – *Anthidium caucasicum* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1862 – *Anthidium vigilans* SMITH, 1878 – *Anthidium florentinum* var. *hispanicum* MOCSÁRY, 1884 – *Anthidium florentinum* var. *rufescente* DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1908 – *Anthidium florentinum* ssp. *cypricum* MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1949 – *Anthidium helianthinum* WU, 2004.
4. **Anthidium (Anthidium) loti** PERRIS, 1852.
Apis variegata FABRICIUS, 1781 – *Apis varia* GMELIN, 1790 – *Anthidium sinuatum* LEPELETIER DE SAINT FARGEAU, 1841 – *Anthidium regulare* EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Anthidium mosaicum* COSTA, 1863 – *Anthidium meridionale* GIRAUD, 1863 – *Anthidium quadriseriatum* KRIECHBAUMER, 1873 – *Anthidium quadriseriatum* var. *circumcinctum* KRIECHBAUMER, 1873 – *Anthidium variegatum* var. *incisum* FRIESE, 1917.
5. **Anthidium (Anthidium) manicatum** (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Apis pervigil HARRIS, 1776 – *Apis maculata* FABRICIUS, 1781 – *Apis fulvipes* VILLERS, 1789 – *Apis modesta* CHRIST, 1791 – *Apis amoenita* CHRIST, 1791 – *Apis uncatata* SCHRANK, 1802 – *Anthidium maculatum* PANZER, 1806 – *Anthidium maculatum* LATREILLE, 1806 – *Anthidium marginatum* LATREILLE, 1809 – *Anthidium obtusatum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium barbarum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium productum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium manicatum* var. *nigrithorax* DALLA TORRE, 1877 – *Anthidium manicatum* var. *fasciatum* SCHIRMER, 1915 – *Anthidium manicatum* var. *nasicolle* FRIESE, 1917

– *Anthidium manicatum* var. *luteum* GRIBODO, 1924 – *Anthidium manicatum subcrenulata* ALFKEN, 1931 – *Anthidium manicatum cyrenaica* VAN DER ZANDEN, 1992 – *Anthidium manicatum gribodoi* SCHWARZ & GUSENLEITNER, 2003 – *Anthidium manicatum hissaricum* MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1939.

6. **Anthidium (Anthidium) montanum** MORAWITZ, 1864.
Anthidium flavomaculatum FRIESE, 1897 – ? *Anthidium reichardti* GUSSAKOVSKIJ, 1928 – *Anthidium montanum* ssp. *reichardti* GUSSAKOVSKIJ, 1928 – *Anthidium montanum pamirensis* (sic) ALFKEN, 1931.
 7. **Anthidium (Proanthidium) oblongatum** (ILLIGER, 1806).
Apis manicata PANZER, 1798 – *Anthophora oblongata* ILLIGER, 1806 – *Anthidium oblongatum* LATREILLE, 1809 – *Anthidium oblongatum* var. *nigrum* FRIESE, 1897 – *Anthidium oblongatum* var. *luteum* DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1915 – *Anthidium oblongatum xanthurum* COCKERELL, 1925 – *Anthidium oblongatum australe* ALFKEN, 1937 – *Anthidium oblongatum* var. *flavens* MÓCZÁR, 1956 – *Proanthidium tornense* TKALCÚ, 1966 – *Anthidium oblongatum berberum* WARNCKE, 1980.
 8. **Anthidium (Anthidium) punctatum** LATREILLE, 1809.
Anthidium minus NYLANDER, 1848 – ? *Anthidium punctatum senile* EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Anthidium greyi* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1862 – *Anthidium albidulum* CHEVRIER, 1872 – *Anthidium nitidulum* MORAWITZ, 1893 – *Anthidium Mayeti* PÉREZ, 1895 – *Anthidium punctatum* var. *albofasciatum* FRIESE, 1897 – *Anthidium punctatum* var. *fulvipes* FRIESE, 1897 – ? *Anthidium kohlii* FRIESE, 1897 – *Anthidium punctatum* var. *bequaerti* ALFKEN, 1914 – *Anthidium amanusense* DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1915 – *Anthidium punctatum* var. *ariasi* DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1915 – *Anthidium kohlii* var. *nigritulum* FRIESE, 1917 – *Anthidium punctatum* var. *fulvipes* KOKUJEV, 1927 – *Anthidium punctatum* var. *suecicum* ALFKEN, 1927 – ? *Anthidium baicalense* COCKERELL, 1928 – *Anthidium punctatum oreophilum* POPOV, 1948 – *Anthidium punctatum zaidamense* POPOV, 1948 – *Anthidium punctatum himalayaense* WU, 1982.
 9. **Anthidium (Anthidium) septemspinosum** LEPELETIER, 1841.
Anthidium dinurum COCKERELL, 1928 – *Anthidium nigripes* EVERS-MANN, 1852.
 10. **Anthidium (Anthidium) taeniatum** LATREILLE, 1809.
Anthidium fasciatum LATREILLE, 1809 – *Anthidium sulphureum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium affine* MORAWITZ, 1873 – *Anthidium affine* var. *monile* FRIESE, 1897 – *Anthidium affine* var. *nostrum* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1893 – *Anthidium frontevillosum* PASTEELS, 1969.
 11. **Anthidium (Proanthidium) undulatum** DOURS, 1873.
Anthidium littorale MORAWITZ, 1874 – *Proanthidium undulatum holozonicum* MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1939 – *Proanthidium undulatum wahrmani* MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1948 – *Anthidium undulatum creticum* TKALCÚ, 2003.
- Genre **Chelostoma** LATREILLE, 1809.
2. **Chelostoma (Foveosmia) distinctum** (STÖCKHERT, 1929).
Chelostoma cantabrica BENOIST, 1936.
 3. **Chelostoma (Chelostoma) emarginatum** (NYLANDER, 1856).
Heriades appendiculatum MORAWITZ, 1980 – *Chelostoma angustata* CHEVRIER, 1872 – *Chelostoma incertum* PÉREZ, 1890.
 4. **Chelostoma (Chelostoma) florissome** (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Chelostoma maxillosum (LINNAEUS, 1767) – *Chelostoma culmorum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Eriades maxillosus* (LINNAEUS, 1758).
 5. **Chelostoma (Foveosmia) foveolatum** (MORAWITZ, 1868).
Heriades intermedia CHEVRIER, 1889.
 9. **Chelostoma (Gyrodromella) nasutum** PÉREZ, 1895.
Eriades truncatus FRIESE, 1897.
 10. **Chelostoma (Gyrodromella) rapunculi** (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Chelostoma nigricorne (NYLANDER, 1848) – *Chelostoma fuliginosum* (PANZER, 1798) – *Chelostoma casularum* (CHEVRIER, 1872) – *Chelostoma archaensis* (COCKERELL, 1928) – *Chelostoma platyodonta* (COCKERELL, 1928) – *Chelostoma proximum* SCHLETTERER, 1889 – *Chelostoma confusum* (BENOIST, 1934).
- Genre **Coelioxys** LATREILLE, 1809.
3. **Coelioxys (Paracoelioxys) alatus** FÖRSTER, 1853.
Coelioxys montandoni GRIBODO, 1884.
 7. **Coelioxys (Allocoelioxys) caudatus** SPINOLA, 1838.
Coelioxys foersteri MORAWITZ, 1872.
 8. **Coelioxys (Melissoctonia) conoideus** (ILLIGER, 1806).
Coelioxys vectis CURTIS, 1831.
 10. **Coelioxys (Allocoelioxys) echinatus** FÖRSTER, 1853.
Coelioxys rufocaudata SMITH, 1854 – *Coelioxys octodentata* LEPELETIER, 1841.
 14. **Coelioxys (Paracoelioxys) inermis** (KIRBY, 1802).
Coelioxys acuminata NYLANDER, 1852.
 15. **Coelioxys (Coelioxys) lanceolatus** NYLANDER, 1852.
Coelioxys patula PÉREZ, 1884.

17. *Coelioxys (Allocoelioxys) obtusus* PÉREZ, 1884.

Coelioxys ruficauda LEPELETIER, 1841.

19. *Coelioxys (Coelioxys) quadridentatus* (LINNAEUS, 1758).

Coelioxys conica (Linnaeus, 1758) – *Coelioxys agilis* (HARRIS, 1776) – *Coelioxys acuminata* (GMELIN, 1790).

Genre *Dioxys* LEPELETIER & SERVILE, 1825.

1. *Dioxys cinctus* (JURINE, 1807).

Dioxys maura LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Dioxys pyrenaica* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Dioxys cruenta* GERSTÄCKER, 1869 – *Dioxys spinigera* PÉREZ, 1884.

2. *Dioxys moestus* COSTA, 1883.

Dioxys rotundata PÉREZ, 1884.

Genre *Hoplitis* KLUG, 1807.

1. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) acuticornis* (DUFOR & PERRIS, 1840).

Hoplitis dentiventris (MORAWITZ, 1877).

2. *Hoplitis (Hoplitis) adunca* (PANZER, 1798).

Hoplitis spinolae (LEPELETIER, 1841) *nec* (SCHENCK, 1851) – *Hoplitis marginella* (LEPELETIER, 1841), mâle *nec* femelle – *Hoplitis aduncoides* STRAND, 1910, mâle *nec* femelle.

4. *Hoplitis (Hoplitis) annulata* (LATREILLE, 1811).

Hoplitis pruinosa (DESTEFANI, 1887).

5. *Hoplitis (Hoplitis) anthocopoides* (SCHENCK, 1853).

Hoplitis hybrida (PÉREZ, 1879) – *Hoplitis spinolae* (SCHENCK, 1851) *nec* (LEPETIER, 1841) – *Hoplitis romana* (MORICE, 1901) – *Hoplitis caementaria* (GERSTÄCKER, 1869) – *Hoplitis claripennis* (SCHENCK, 1870).

6. *Hoplitis (Anthocopa) antigae* (PÉREZ, 1895).

Anthocopa contigua PÉREZ (*nomen nudum*).

7. *Hoplitis (Hoplitis) benoisti* (ALFKEN, 1935).

Osmia grinincensis BENOIST, 1969 – *Hoplitis morawitzi* (PÉREZ, 1879) *nec* (GERSTÄCKER, 1869).

8. *Hoplitis (Hoplitis) bihamata* (COSTA, 1885).

Osmia corsica FERTON, 1901.

9. *Hoplitis (Anthocopa) bisulca* (GERSTÄCKER, 1869).

Osmia lanosa Pérez, 1879 – *Hoplitis cretaea* (TKALCŮ, 1992).

10. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) brachypogon* (PÉREZ, 1879).

Osmia seyrigi BENOIST, 1934.

12. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) claviventris* (THOMSON, 1872).

Hoplitis leucomelana auct. *nec* KIRBY, 1802.

14. *Hoplitis (Anthocopa) cristatula* (VAN DER ZANDEN, 1990)

Anthocopa cristata FONSCOLOMBE, 1846.

15. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) curtula* (PÉREZ, 1895).

Osmia bofilli PÉREZ, 1905.

18. *Hoplitis (Anthocopa) fasciculata* (ALFKEN, 1934).

Osmia idalia MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1949.

21. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) leucomelana* (KIRBY, 1802).

Osmia parvula DUFOR & PERRIS, 1840.

23. *Hoplitis (Hoplitis) loti* (MORAWITZ, 1867).

Osmia difformis PÉREZ, 1879 – *Hoplitis morawitzi* (GERSTÄCKER, 1869) *nec* (PÉREZ, 1879).

25. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) mitis* (NYLANDER, 1852).

Osmia montivaga (MORAWITZ, 1872) – *Hoplitis laevifrons* (PÉREZ, 1840) *nec* (MORAWITZ, 1872).

30. *Hoplitis (Anthocopa) papaveris* (LATREILLE, 1799).

Anthocopa pacifica EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Anthocopa hyalipennis* LEPELETIER, 1841.

31. *Hoplitis (Anthocopa) perezi* (FERTON, 1895).

Anthocopa convolvuli (DUCKE, 1899).

32. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) praestans* (MORAWITZ, 1893).

Hoplitis lineola (PÉREZ, 1896).

33. *Hoplitis (Hoplitis) ravouxi* (PÉREZ, 1902).

Hoplitis loti (MORICE, 1901) *nec* (MORAWITZ, 1867) – *Hoplitis rhinotropis* (PÉREZ, 1902) – *Hoplitis brachyceros* (BLÜTHGEN, 1920) – *Hoplitis clypeata* SLADEN, 1916 – *Hoplitis rhinoceros* (GIRAUD, 1861).

34. *Hoplitis (Formicapis) robusta* (NYLANDER, 1848).

Hoplitis clypeata SLADEN, 1916 – *Hoplitis rhinoceros* (GIRAUD, 1861) – *Heriades robusta* NYLANDER, 1848.

36. *Hoplitis (Hoplitis) stecki* (FREY-GESSNER, 1908).

Hoplitis mucida auct. *nec* (DOURS, 1873) – *Hoplitis mucida stecki* (FREY-GESSNER, 1908) – *Hoplitis mucidoides* VAN DER ZANDEN, 1990.

38. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) tridentata* (DUFOR & PERRIS, 1840).

Osmia asensioi TKALCŮ, 1975.

39. *Hoplitis (Alcidamea) tuberculata* (NYLANDER, 1848).

Osmia signata (EVERSMANN, 1852) – *Hoplitis hamata* (EVERSMANN, 1852) – *Hoplitis signata* (COCKERELL, 1931).

40. *Hoplitis (Anthocopa) villosa* (SCHENCK, 1853).

Osmia platycera GERSTÄCKER, 1869.

Genre *Icteranthidium* MICHENER, 1948.

1. *Icteranthidium grohmanni* (SPINOLA, 1838).

Anthidium numida (sic) LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium latreillei* (sic) LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium latreillei* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium provinciale* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium rubiginosum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium comptum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium lepeletieri* FONSCOLOMBE, 1846 – *Anthidium KLUGII* LUCAS, 1846 – *Anthidium coronatum* SMITH, 1854 – *Anthidium latreillei* var. *obscurum* DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1908 – *Icteranthidium tergale* PASTEELS, 1969.

2. *Icteranthidium laterale* (LATREILLE, 1809).

Anthidium scutellare LATREILLE, 1809 – *Anthidium quadrilobum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium auripes* EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Anthidium annulare* SCHENCK, 1870 – *Anthidium sexmaculatum* CHEVRIER, 1872 – *Anthidium perrisii* DOURS, 1873 – *Anthidium laterale* var. *confluens* ALFKEN, 1931 – *Anthidium ifranicum* COCKERELL, 1931 – *Icteranthidium laterale scutellare* (LATREILLE, 1809).

Genre *Megachile* LATREILLE, 1802.

1. *Megachile (Creightonella) albisecta* (KLUG, 1817).

Megachile sericans FONSCOLOMBE, 1832 – *Megachile dufouri* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Megachile odontura* (SMITH, 1849) – *Megachile carinulata* COSTA, 1882.

2. *Megachile (Chalicodoma) albocristata* SMITH, 1853.

Chalicodoma serrata SMITH, 1853 *nec* 1878 – *Chalicodoma lefebvrei tristis* FRIESE, 1898.

3. *Megachile (Megachile) alpicola* ALFKEN, 1924.

Megachile rubtzovi COCKERELL, 1928.

4. *Megachile (Xanthosarus) analis* NYLANDER, 1852.

Megachile albicilla EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Megachile angarensis* COCKERELL, 1928.

5. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) apicalis* SPINOLA, 1808.

Megachile mixta COSTA, 1863 – *Megachile dimidiiventris* DOURS, 1873 – *Megachile massiliensis* PÉREZ, 1902.

6. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) argentata* (FABRICIUS, 1793).

Megachile argyrea COCKERELL, 1931 – *Megachile pilidens* ALFKEN, 1924 – *Megachile schmiedeknechti* COSTA, 1884.

10. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) deceptoris* PÉREZ, 1890.

Megachile mogadorensis BENOIST, 1934.

13. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) flabellipes* PÉREZ, 1895.

Megachile albopicta SMITH, 1853.

15. *Megachile (Xanthosarus) giraudi* GERSTÄCKER, 1869.

Megachile bicoloriventris MOCSÁRY, 1878 – *Megachile atlantica* BENOIST, 1934.

16. *Megachile (Xanthosarus) lagopoda* (LINNAEUS, 1760).

Megachile lagopus (GMELIN, 1790) – *Megachile pyrina* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Megachile baleina* COCKERELL, 1928.

17. *Megachile (Megachile) lapponica* THOMSON, 1872.

Megachile melanopyga amaguella COCKERELL, 1924.

18. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) leachella* CURTIS, 1828.

Megachile argentata auct. *nec* (FABRICIUS, 1793) – *Megachile argentata* var. *fossoria* FERTON, 1908 – *Megachile dorsalis* PÉREZ, 1879 – *Megachile discriminata* PÉREZ, 1902 – *Megachile ichnusae* REB-MANN, 1968.

19. *Megachile (Chalicodoma) lefebvrei* LEPELETIER, 1841.

Chalicodoma luctuosa DOURS, 1873 – *Chalicodoma muraria* var. *variabilis* FRIESE, 1920

20. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) leucomalla* GERSTÄCKER, 1869.

Megachile excellens MORAWITZ, 1872.

21. *Megachile (Megachile) ligniseca* (KIRBY, 1802).

Megachile borealis NIEMELÄ, 1936.

22. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) marginata* SMITH, 1853.

Megachile picicornis MORAWITZ, 1877 – *Megachile perezi* MOCSÁRY, 1887.

23. *Megachile (Xanthosarus) maritima* (KIRBY, 1802).

Phyllotoma manicata DUMÉRIL, 1860 – *Megachile fulvescens* SMITH, 1853 *nec* WALKER, 1871 – *Megachile flaviventris* SMITH, 1853.

24. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) melanogaster* EVERS-MANN, 1852.

Megachile sexmaculata ALFKEN, 1924.

25. *Megachile (Megachile) melanopyga* COSTA, 1863.

Megachile vestita GIRAUD, 1863.

26. *Megachile (Xanthosarus) nigriventris* SCHENCK, 1870.

Megachile ursula GERSTÄCKER, 1869 – *Megachile hasticornis* COCKERELL, 1924.

29. *Megachile (Chalicodoma) parietina* (GEOFFROY IN FOURCROY, 1785).

Megachile muraria (OLIVIER, 1789) – *Chalicodoma bryorum* (SCHRANK, 1781) 1862 – *Chalicodoma muraria* (RETZIUS, 1783) – *Chalicodoma caementaria* (MEINECKE, 1784) – *Chalicodoma varians* (ROSSI, 1792) – *Chalicodoma leucopogonatum* DOURS, 1873 – *Chalicodoma savignyi* (RADOSZKOWSKI, 1874) – *Chalicodoma valesina* ALFKEN, 1931.

30. *Megachile (Megachile) pilicrus* MORAWITZ, 1877.
Megachile vicina MOCSÁRY, 1879.
31. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) pusilla* PÉREZ, 1884.
Megachile atratula REBMANN, 1968 – *Megachile concinna* auct. nec SMITH, 1879 – *Megachile striatella* REBMANN, 1968.
33. *Megachile (Chalicodoma) pyrenaica* LEPELETIER, 1841.
Chalicodoma rufitarsis (GIRAUD, 1863) nec (LEPELETIER, 1841) – *Chalicodoma pyrrohopeza* GERSTÄCKER, 1869.
34. *Megachile (Eutricharaea) rotundata* (FABRICIUS, 1793).
Megachile pacifica PANZER, 1798 – *Megachile imbecilla* GERSTÄCKER, 1869 – *Megachile pruinosa* PÉREZ, 1897.
35. *Megachile (Chalicodoma) rufescens* (PÉREZ, 1879).
Chalicodoma rufescens PÉREZ, 1879.
37. *Megachile (Chalicodoma) sicula* (ROSSI, 1792).
Chalicodoma pereziana DALLA TORRE, 1896.
38. *Megachile (Megachile) versicolor* SMITH, 1844.
Megachile rufiventris SCHENCK, 1851 – *Megachile distincta* PÉREZ, 1897 – *Megachile pilicruriformis* COCKERELL, 1928 – *Megachile semiplea* COCKERELL, 1921.
39. *Megachile (Xanthosarus) willughbiella* (KIRBY, 1802).
Megachile atriventris SCHENCK, 1851 – *Megachile centuncularis* var. *janssoni* ALFKEN, 1926 – *Megachile korotnooi* COCKERELL, 1928.

Genre *Osmia* PANZER, 1806.

4. *Osmia (Hemiosmia) argropyga* PÉREZ, 1879.
Osmia entoprocta PÉREZ, 1896.
5. *Osmia (Helicosmia) aurulenta* (PANZER, 1799).
Osmia haematoda (PANZER, 1801) – *Osmia marginella* LEPELETIER, 1841 femelle nec mâle.
7. *Osmia (Osmia) bicornis* (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Osmia rufa (LINNAEUS, 1758).
8. *Osmia (Hoplosmia) bidentata* MORAWITZ, 1876.
Anthocopa affinis (FRIVALDSKY, 1876).
9. *Osmia (Metallinella) brevicornis* (FABRICIUS, 1798).
Osmia panzeri MORAWITZ, 1869 – *Osmia atrocaerula* (SCHILLER, 1849).
10. *Osmia (Helicosmia) caerulecens* (LINNAEUS, 1758).
Osmia aenea (LINNAEUS, 1761) – *Osmia purpurea* CRESSON, 1864 – *Osmia melanippa* SPINOLA, 1808 – *Osmia dutti* COCKERELL, 1922.
11. *Osmia (Pyrosmia) cephalotes* MORAWITZ, 1870.
Osmia pulsata BUYSSON, 1899 – *Osmia bacillus* PÉREZ, 1879/
15. *Osmia (Helicosmia) dimidiata* MORAWITZ, 1870.
Osmia cephalotes PÉREZ, 1879 nec MORAWITZ, 1870.
18. *Osmia (Pyrosmia) ferruginea* LATREILLE, 1811.
Osmia metallica LUCAS, 1849 – *Osmia igneopurpurea* COSTA, 1882.
19. *Osmia (Pyrosmia) gallarum* SPINOLA, 1808.
Osmia ruborum DUFOUR & PERRIS, 1840 – *Osmia lapidistructor* FERTON, 1921.
20. *Osmia (Melanosmia) inermis* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1838).
Osmia vulpecula GERSTÄCKER, 1869.
22. *Osmia (Helicosmia) latreillei* (SPINOLA, 1806).
Osmia nasidens LATREILLE, 1811.
23. *Osmia (Helicosmia) leaiana* (KIRBY, 1802).
Osmia ventralis (PANZER, 1798) – *Osmia confusa* MORAWITZ, 1869 – *Osmia bidens* PÉREZ, 1879 – *Osmia solskyi* MORAWITZ – *Osmia aduncooides* STRAND, 1910 mâle nec femelle.
24. *Osmia (Hoplosmia) ligurica* MORAWITZ, 1868.
Anthocopa detrita (PÉREZ, 1879).
26. *Osmia (Helicosmia) melanogaster* SPINOLA, 1808.
Osmia notata auct. nec FABRICIUS, 1804 – *Osmia aterrima* MORAWITZ, 1872 – *Osmia incerta* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1876.
30. *Osmia (Nasutosmia) nasuta* FRIESE, 1899.
Osmia rhynchaena PÉREZ, 1905.
31. *Osmia (Melanosmia) nigriventris* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1838).
Osmia frigida SMITH, 1853 – *Osmia corticalis* GERSTÄCKER, 1869 – *Osmia baicalensis* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1867.
32. *Osmia (Helicosmia) niveata* (FABRICIUS, 1804).
Osmia fulviventris (PANZER, 1798).
34. *Osmia (Melanosmia) parietina* CURTIS, 1828.
Osmia angustula ZETTERSTEDT, 1838 – *Osmia vankovitzii* RADOSZKOWSKI, 1887.
39. *Osmia (Helicosmia) signata* ERICHSON, 1835.
Osmia vidua GERSTÄCKER, 1869 – *Osmia cincta* DOURS, 1873 – *Osmia costaniana* DALLA TORRE & FRIESE, 1895 – *Osmia atriventris* COSTA, 1883.
40. *Osmia (Hoplosmia) spinulosa* (KIRBY, 1802).
Anthocopa euchreiformis (RADOSZKOWSKI, 1882).

42. *Osmia (Pyrosmia) submicans* MORAWITZ, 1870.
Osmia giraudi (SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1886).
43. *Osmia (Tergosmia) tergestensis* DUCKE, 1897.
Osmia atlantica BENOIST, 1934 – *Osmia ononides* FERTON, 1897 – *Osmia rondoui* PÉREZ, 1902 – *Osmia wolhynica* NOSKIEWICZ, 1922.
45. *Osmia (Melanosmia) uncinata* GERSTÄCKER, 1869.
Osmia laticeps THOMSON, 1872 nec FRIESE, 1899.
47. *Osmia (Pyrosmia) viridana* MORAWITZ, 1874.
Osmia angulata PÉREZ, 1896.
48. *Osmia (Melanosmia) xanthomelana* (KIRBY, 1802).
Osmia chrysolina (PANZER, 1812) – *Osmia fuciformis* LATREILLE, 1811.

Genre *Protosmia* DUCKE, 1900.

3. *Protosmia (Nanosmia) minutula* (PÉREZ, 1896).
Protosmia cataniae STRAND, 1921 – *Protosmia pumila* (PÉREZ, 1896).

Genre *Pseudoanthidium* FRIESE, 1898.

1. *Pseudoanthidium (Exanthidium) eximium* (GIRAUD, 1863).
Pseudoanthidium excisum MOCSÁRY, 1884 – *Anthidium eximium* GIRAUD, 1863.
2. *Pseudoanthidium (Royanthidium) melanurum* (KLUG, 1832).
Anthidium nigricolle MORAWITZ, 1876 – *Anthidium dilobum* PÉREZ, 1895 – *Anthidium moricei* FRIESE, 1911 – *Anthidium nigricolle* var. *flaviventre* FRIESE, 1917 – *Anthidium nigricolle* var. *flavicolle* FRIESE, 1917.
3. *Pseudoanthidium (Pseudoanthidium) nanum* (MOCSÁRY, 1881).
Apis liturata PANZER, 1801 – *Anthidium reptans* EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Anthidium nanum* MOCSÁRY, 1880 – ?*Anthidium tenellum* var. *grandii* ALFKEN, 1936.
4. *Pseudoanthidium (Royanthidium) reticulatum* (MOCSÁRY, 1884).
Anthidium tegulare MORAWITZ, 1886 – *Anthidium mocsaryi* FRIESE, 1897. – *Anthidium reticulatum* kindenmani MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1954.
5. *Pseudoanthidium (Pseudoanthidium) scapulare* (LATREILLE, 1809).
Anthidium frontale LEPELETIER, 1841.
6. *Pseudoanthidium (Pseudoanthidium.) stigmaticorne* (DOURS, 1873).
? *Stelis leucostoma* COSTA, 1883 – ? *Anthidium peregrinum* COSTA, 1885 – ? *Anthidium fraternum* PÉREZ, 1895 – *Anthidium astillero* DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1915 – *Paranthidiellum karakalense* POPOV, 1952 – ? *Pseudoanthidium alpinum gregoriense* NOBILE, 1990.

Genre *Rhodanthidium* ISENSEE, 1927.

1. *Rhodanthidium (Asianthidium) caturigense* (GIRAUD, 1863).
Anthidium ducale MORAWITZ, 1876 – *Anthidium moreense* FRIESE, 1917 – *Anthidium caturigense* var. *pyrenaicum* ALFKEN, 1927 – *Anthidium moreense* ssp. *jerusalemicum* MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1938 – *Axillanthidium axillare* PASTEELS, 1969.
2. *Rhodanthidium (Rhodanthidium) infuscatum* (ERICHSON, 1835).
Anthidium bellicosum LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Stelis nemorosa* GISTEL, 1857.
3. *Rhodanthidium (Rhodanthidium) septemdentatum* (LATREILLE, 1809).
Megachile florentina SPINOLA, 1806 – *Anthidium rufiventre* BRULLÉ, 1832 – *Anthidium quadridentatum* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium fuscipenne* Lepeletier, 1841 – *Anthidium sexlineatum* CHEVRIER, 1872 – *Anthidium binominatum* SMITH, 1854 – *Anthidium quadridentatum* GIRAUD, 1857 – *Anthidium septemdentatum* var. *faciale* FRIESE, 1917 – *Anthidium nigrosetosum* STANŮK, 1968.
4. *Rhodanthidium (Rhodanthidium) sticticum* (FABRICIUS, 1787).
Anthidium sticticum var. *amismiziana* DUSMET Y ALONSO, 1915.

Genre *Stelis* PANZER, 1806.

1. *Stelis (Heterostelis) annulata* (LEPELETIER, 1841).
Stelis freygessneri FRIESE, 1885.
2. *Stelis (Stelis) breviscula* (NYLANDER, 1848).
Stelis pygmaea SCHENCK, 1853 – *Heriades paxillorum* CHEVRIER, 1872 – *Stelis pusilla* MORAWITZ, 1867.
5. *Stelis (Pseudostelis) minima* SCHENCK, 1861.
Stelis unicolor ALFKEN, 1944.
6. *Stelis (Pseudostelis) minuta* LEPELETIER & AUDINET-SERVILLE, 1825.
Stelis nana SCHENCK, 1853.
7. *Stelis (Stelis) murina* PÉREZ, 1884.
Stelis cassiopaea SAUNDERS, 1908 – *Stelis murina* ssp. *cretica* MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1963.
8. *Stelis (Stelidomorpha) nasuta* (LATREILLE, 1809).
Anthidium nasale LATREILLE, 1809
10. *Stelis (Stelis) ornatula* (KLUG, 1807).
Trachusa sexpunctata HUMMEL, 1826 – *Stelis octomaculata* SMITH, 1843 – *Stelis sexsignata* COSTA, 1858 – *Stelis ornatula* var. *immaculata* NOSKIEWICZ,

1926 – *Stelis ornata gussakovskii* POPOV, 1933 – *Stelis ornata montana* POPOV, 1933 – *Stelis ornata* ssp. *oreophila* POPOV, 1935.

11. *Stelis (Stelis) phaeoptera* (KIRBY, 1802).

Stelis aterrima CHRIST, 1791 nec PANZER, 1798 – *Apis stigma* CHRIST, 1791 – *Stelis meridionalis* POPOV, 1932 – *Stelis phaeoptera* ssp. *meridionalis* POPOV, 1933.

12. *Stelis (Stelis) punctulatissima* (KIRBY, 1802).

Stelis aterrima (PANZER, 1798) nec CHRIST, 1791 – *Stelis aterrima* ssp. *hellenica* MAVROMOUSTAKIS, 1959 – *Stelis beaumonti* NOSKIEWICZ, 1962 – *Stelis moravica* TKALCŮ, 1970.

13. *Stelis (Protostelis) signata* (LATREILLE, 1809).

Anthidium parvulum LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Stelis* STRIGATA Kriechbaumer, 1874 – *Stelis signata* var. *flavescens* FRIESE, 1925 – *Stelis signata* ssp. *eremica* ALFKEN, 1938.

14. *Stelis (Stelis) simillima* MORAWITZ, 1876.

Stelis cognata KOHL, 1892 – *Stelis genalis* PASTEELS, 1969.

Genre ***Trachusa*** PANZER, 1804.

1. *Trachusa (Trachusa) byssina* (PANZER, 1798).

Trachusa serratulae (PANZER, 1804) – *Diphysis pyrenaica* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Megachile resinana* SCHILLING, 1849 – *Megachile rotundiventris* PERRIS, 1852 – *Osmia bluethgeni* MAIDL, 1922 – *Trachusa serratulae* var. *seitzi* COCKERELL, 1925 – *Megachile kychtacenensis* COCKERELL, 1928.

2. *Trachusa (Paraanthidium) integra* (Eversmann, 1852).

Anthidium integrum EVERS-MANN, 1852 – *Anthidium interruptum* FABRICIUS, 1781 (*partim*).

3. *Trachusa (Paraanthidium) interrupta* (FABRICIUS, 1781).

Synonymes - *Anthidium flavilabre* LATREILLE, 1809 – *Anthidium dufouri* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium luteipes* LEPELETIER, 1841 – *Anthidium curvipes* SCHMID, 1872 – *Anthidium melanostoma* COSTA, 1884.

4. *Trachusa (Archianthidium) laeiventris* (DOURS, 1873).

Anthidium laeiventre DOURS, 1873 – *Anthidium atlanticum* BENOIST, 1934.

Famille **Melittidae** SCHENCK, 1860.

Sous-famille ***Dasypodainae*** BÖRNER, 1919.

Genre ***Dasypoda*** LATREILLE, 1802.

1. *Dasypoda (Heterodasyopoda) albimana* PÉREZ, 1905.

Dasypoda bolivari QUILIS, 1928.

2. *Dasypoda (Megadasyopoda) argentata* PANZER, 1809.

Dasypoda carinata PÉREZ, 1896.

5. *Dasypoda (Dasyopoda) dusmeti* QUILIS, 1928.

Dasypoda niveocincta NOSKIEWICZ, 1959.

6. *Dasypoda (Dasyopoda) hirtipes* (FABRICIUS, 1793).

Dasypoda plumipes (PANZER, 1797) – *Dasyopoda altercator* (Harris, 1780) – *Dasyopoda illegalis* SCHULZ, 1906.

8. *Dasyopoda (Heterodasyopoda) pyrotrichia* FÖRSTER, 1855.

Dasyopoda nigra QUILIS, 1928.

9. *Dasyopoda (Megadasyopoda) visnaga* (ROSSI, 1790).

Andrena distincta ROSSI, 1790 – *Andrena visnaga* ROSSI, 1790.